

D4.3 Implementation of R8: STEM Lessons

WP4

Virtualware

Report

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GLOSSARY

Digital Project: A sequence of teaching units and activities with the aim of acquiring a series of specific skills and knowledge based on using technology as a learning facilitation tool, contents and online references to reinforce knowledge and free digital tools for the creation of new contents. With a double objective; on one hand, allowing to know how to look for information from reliable sources to improve knowledge about different subjects and on the other hand, learning how to use this information and the information generated by each person to create new quality content

STEM: a curriculum based on the idea of educating students in these four specific disciplines — science, technology, engineering and mathematics — in an interdisciplinary and applied approach. Rather than teach the four disciplines as separate and discrete subjects, STEM integrates them into a cohesive learning paradigm based on real-world applications emphasizing the application of knowledge to real-life situations. A lesson or unit in a STEM class is typically based around finding a solution to a real-world problem and tends to emphasize project-based learning.

STEAM: A variation of STEM is STEAM, which includes an 'A' for art and design. The arts animate learning because they are inherently experiential and because of their potential to develop creative and critical thinking skills in students. Artistic design is becoming an important part of STEM education since creativity is an essential part of innovation. Many STEM lessons involve building models and simulating situations. A good STEM lesson ensures that students understand the connection to the real world. This way, STEM learning materials evolve to STEAM lessons (STEM plus arts).

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The objective of WP4 is to develop contents and innovative methodologies to foster behavioral changes in waste producers, according to the objectives and goals of the project.

This document describes the work done under Task 4.2 Learning materials within WP4 CREATION OF INNOVATIVE SOCIAL ACTIONS which main responsible is Virtualware with the contribution and help of Fundación DEUSTO, ZAMUDIOko Udala, National Technical University of Athens - NTUA, University of PATRAS and Agencia d'ecologia Urbana de Barcelona (BCN) partners.

The main objective of D4.3 is:

O4.2. Design innovative learning methods to foster the empowerment of citizen and stakeholder (Result R8).

D4.3 is focused on describing the general concepts associated with digital learning materials for enhancing the understanding of waste management concerns at schools and more specifically, the description of - R8: STEAM Lessons - 4 digital STEAM lessons with their associated Digital Projects (Digital Project 1 associated with STEAM Lesson1 and Digital Project 2 Linked with STEAM Lessons 2,3&4) and activities for fostering a better understanding of waste-generation prevention actions. All these resources will be accessible from the web page of the project as well as in relevant public repositories for teaching materials.

The outcome STEAM lessons described in this document are also available at:

Materi als	Scientix	OERCOMMONS
Digital projec t 1	http://www.scientix.eu/resources/details?resourceId=23044	https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/module/43658
STEAM 1	http://www.scientix.eu/resources/details?resourceId=23044	https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/module/43658
Digital projec t 2	http://www.scientix.eu/resources/details?resourceId=23045	https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/module/43659

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STEAM 2	http://www.scientix.eu/resources/details?resourceId=23045	https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/module/43659
STEAM 3	http://www.scientix.eu/resources/details?resourceId=23045	https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/module/43659
STEAM 4	http://www.scientix.eu/resources/details?resourceId=23045	https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/module/43659

1 INTRODUCTION

This document describes the work done under Task 4.2 Learning materials within WP4 CREATION OF INNOVATIVE SOCIAL ACTIONS which main responsible is Virtualware with the contribution and help of Fundación DEUSTO, ZAMUDIOkO Udala, National Technical University of Athens - NTUA, University of PATRAS and Agencia d'ecologia Urbana de Barcelona (BCN) partners.

The work performed in this task is directly related with WP1, WP2 (T2.4- Long Term Planning and T2.5 - Incentive System Planner to Foster Circular Economy) and WP4 (T4.1 - Generation of the pilots' social programme.). On the other hand, information provided in deliverables D1.1- Pilots Planning documentation, D1.3 – Sustainability Assessment Models, D2.7- Technical Documentation of R3: Planning Module; D2.10 - Implementation of R4: Circular Economy Planning Module and D4.1 - Implementation of R17: Non ICT Innovative Social Actions - is a value added input for the work to be performed in this task.

The objective of WP4 is to develop contents and innovative methodologies to foster behavioral changes in waste producers, according to the objectives and goals of the project.

In this context, one of the foreseen outcome deliverables is:

- D4.3 Implementation of R8: STEAM Lessons

The main objective of D4.3 is:

- O4.2. Design innovative learning methods to foster the empowerment of citizen and stakeholder (Result R8).
-

These materials have been developed during the T4.2 Digital learning materials, outcomes are divided in the following way:

- 6 digital project scenarios
- 4 digital STEAM lessons
- 4 mobile location-based games

These materials will be developed according to the associated work plan & delivery dates:

LEARNING MATERIAL	Number of Items	Delivery Date
Digital project	6	September 2018
STEAM Lessons * ¹	4	December 2017. One of them in September/November of 2017 ²
Mobile games	4	September 2018

Table 1. Workplan and deadlines

D4.3 is focused on describing the general concepts associated with digital learning materials for enhancing the understanding of waste management concerns at schools and more specifically, the description of - R8: STEAM Lessons - 4 **digital STEAM** lessons with their associated Digital Projects (Digital Project 1 and Digital Project 2) and activities for fostering a better understanding of waste-generation prevention actions.

The teaching units will be designed according to the standards defined in Task 7.2. The teaching units will be available in the following languages: English, Spanish and Greek. In this deliverable only, the standardized version in English will be provided because the aim is to make the reader able to understand the work performed and to provide a user guide to deal with these educational materials.

A specific section has been included in this deliverable to explain the monitoring methodology for the educational materials used in schools. The evaluation of the effectiveness of the teaching materials generated in this deliverable is also reported with in a real class trial and the description of the integration work done with other solutions aligned the specific strategies regarding educational centre/schools. This input information is extensively described in D4.2 - Implementation of R17 – ICT based Innovative Social Actions. Results obtained will be collected in the corresponding monitoring reports (D1.5 – Deployment & Integration Report, D1.6 – Preliminary Test Report and D1.7 – Full Test Report).

Finally, all the educational resources created and reported along this deliverable D4.3 will be accessible for public use via the project web page - waste4think.eu/. In order to spread out project results educational materials will also be available via main well-known educational

¹ To manage in a efficient way, STEAM lessons will be created in the framework of a vDigital project although it will be available through web site one by one.

² Despite official delivery date is in December of 2017 we consider doing at least one of the STEAM lesson at the beginning of the course. In Zamudio is in September and in Halandri is in November.

platforms such as Scientix³, OER Commons⁴ or WikiToLearn⁵. Dissemination in Scientix is essential. After the evaluation of results obtained in this platform to address remaining platform will be considered to maximize the impact.

The four remaining Digital projects and the four mobile games to be developed within the project will be described in D4.4 - Implementation of R8: Digital Learning Materials to be released at Month21.

³ <http://www.scientix.eu/home>

⁴ <https://www.oercommons.org/>

⁵ <https://www.wikitolearn.org/>

2 GENERAL STRUCTURE OF THE LEARNING MATERIALS

This section describes the general concepts of the learning materials.

Along the project, 6 Digital Projects will be developed. These Digital projects (DP) provide the general framework where different digital learning material to be used will fit to bring an innovative teaching approach. These educational “itineraries” will be adapted to the reality of the schools participating in the project (schools in Zamudio and Halandri) through the appropriate collection of user requirements.

The design of the materials is based on the acquisition of skills and capabilities. A multidisciplinary point of view is adopted for this purpose allowing use them in different subjects or learning steps.

2.1 DIGITAL PROJECT

Digital projects are designed under flexibility and adaptability requirements adapted to the specific teaching framework adopted by each school; age range, competences, knowledge or capacities, etc.

Digital Projects must fit to the following premises:

- Multidisciplinary
- Context of learning: subject, tutorial or space or time dedicated to the acquisition of competences and specific knowledge about the environment
- Work by projects or by STEAM
- Allow different depth level according to age, skills, abilities, knowledge
- Focused beyond content
- Work by competences
- Work inductive thinking
- Allow to apply knowledge and competences in a new context.

The next schema shows how a specific Digital Project is splitted in different STEAM lessons to deeper work with each selected subject, which can work independently or together in a simple and intuitive way depending on each instructional need:

Figure 1. Digital Project structure

The key elements (project name, competences, theme, etc..) are store in a matrix, to identify, organize and find the contents in the content repository as can be seen in the following image:

Figure 2. Content repository matrix

As each digital project is splitted in different STEAM lessons, each STEAM Lesson is also divided in different activities.

2.2 KEY COMPETENCES

The European Commission works with EU countries to strengthen 'key competences' – knowledge, skills, and attitudes that will help learners find personal fulfilment and, later in life, find work and take part in society⁶. These key competences include 'traditional' skills such as communication in one's mother tongue, foreign languages, digital skills, literacy, and basic skills in maths and science, as well as horizontal skills such as learning to learn, social and civic responsibility, initiative and entrepreneurship, cultural awareness, and creativity.

The approach is to promote key competences by:

- providing high-quality learning for all students based on relevant curricula;
- reducing early school-leaving
- increasing early childhood education
- improving support for teachers, school leaders, and teacher educators

In the context of globalisation and the need for competitiveness, there is a serious concern in most of the European countries about the social cohesion and well-being of all individuals. There is a need to enhance active and democratic citizenship which requires that people are informed and concerned about their society and be active in it.

The knowledge, skills and aptitudes of the European workforce are a major factor in the European Union's innovation, productivity and competitiveness. The rapid pace of change and the continuous development of new technologies mean that Europeans must not only keep their specific job-related skills up-to-date, but also possess the generic competences that will enable them to manage change. People's competences also contribute to their motivation and job-satisfaction, thereby affecting the quality of their work and life – thereby bringing added value for the whole organisation of labour and production.

The ways in which people access information and services continue to change. People of all ages need new competences to critically master a whole new digital world, not only by acquiring technical skills, but also by gaining a deeper understanding of the opportunities, challenges and even ethical, legal and societal questions arising from the introduction of new technologies.

⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/education/policy/school/competences_en

It is against this back-drop that the Council and the European Parliament adopted, at the end of 2006, a Recommendation that introduces a European Framework for Key Competences for Lifelong Learning. The Framework identifies and defines, for the first time at the European level, the key competences that citizens require for their personal fulfilment, social inclusion, active citizenship and employability in a knowledge-based society. The Member States' initial education and training systems should support the development of these competences for all young people, and their adult education and training provision should give real opportunities to all adults to learn, update and maintain their competences throughout their lives.

The Recommendation introduces a package of eight key competences that includes not only the 'traditional' competences such as communication in the mother tongue, communication in foreign languages, mathematical competence and basic competences in science and technology, and digital competence, but also the more transversal ones such as learning to learn, social and civic competences, sense of initiative and entrepreneurship, and cultural awareness and expression. Many of the key competences overlap and interlock. Many themes are applied throughout the Framework: critical thinking, creativity, initiative taking, problem solving, risk assessment, decision taking and managing feelings constructively play a major role in all eight key competences.

The Peer Learning Activities (PLAs) organised by the Cluster Key 'Competences – Curriculum Reform' in 2007⁷ have primarily focussed on the first part of the Recommendation that calls for 'ensuring the development of key competences by all young people during their initial education and training', but peer learning has also covered the essential reforms of VET and adult education that are in line with the overall lifelong strategy. Therefore, the following sections look at the lifelong learning strategies with a specific reference to key competences in school curricula and the issues related to the implementation of key competences within school education.

In the following table the list and description of these 8 key competences is provided. In each Digital Project the key competences to be trained will be clearly appointed.

KEY COMPETENCES (EU)		DEFINITION
1	<p><u>Mother Tongue</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communicating in a mother tongue - Verbal and non-verbal Competence and digital communication - Competence in linguistic and literary communication 	Ability to express and interpret concepts, thoughts, feelings, facts and opinions both orally and in writing.

⁷ EDUCATION AND TRAINING 2010 WORK PROGRAMME (2008)- Cluster Key Competences – Curriculum Reform Synthesis Report on Peer Learning Activities in 2007 - http://ec.europa.eu/dgs/education_culture/repository/education/policy/school/doc/peer07_en.pdf

2	<p><u>Communicating in a foreign language</u> - Verbal and non-verbal Competence and digital communication - Competence in linguistic and literary communication</p>	As above, but includes mediation skills (i.e. summarising, paraphrasing, interpreting or translating) and intercultural understanding.
3	<p><u>Mathematical, scientific and technological competence</u> Mathematical Competence Scientific Competence Technological Competence</p>	Sound mastery of numeracy, an understanding of the natural world and an ability to apply knowledge and technology to perceived human needs (such as medicine, transport or communication).
4	<p><u>Digital Competence</u> Digital competence and competence for verbal and non-verbal communications</p>	Confident and critical usage of information and communications technology for work, leisure and communication.
5	<p><u>Learning to learn</u> Learning to learn and thinking competence</p>	Ability to effectively manage one's own learning, either individually or in groups.
6	<p><u>Social and civic competences</u> Competences to live together Social and civic competences</p>	Ability to participate effectively and constructively in one's social and working life and engage in active and democratic participation, especially in increasingly diverse societies.
7	<p><u>Sense of initiative and entrepreneurship</u> Sense of initiative and entrepreneurship</p>	Ability to turn ideas into action through creativity, innovation and risk taking as well as ability to plan and manage projects.
8	<p><u>Cultural awareness and expression</u> <u>Cultural competences</u> <u>Motor competence</u></p>	Ability to appreciate the creative importance of ideas, experiences and emotions in a range of media such as music, literature and visual and performing arts.

Table 2. Key competences

A successful implementation of a curricula based on key competences is not in contradiction with subjects that can allow for a development of in-depth knowledge of a certain discipline and target the acquisition of specific skills. However, if the focus is on the development of a full range of key competences for lifelong learning, subject knowledge should be seen rather as a first step that alone is not enough to fully respond to the needs of a learner in a modern society. The challenge is thus the systematic use of subject matter and the specific skills related to subjects as essential elements of the development of key competences. This requires all teachers, irrespective their subject specialisation, to be aware of and responsible for, developing the key competences of their students in the whole school context.

The experience from PLAs in Flanders, Hungary and Greece shows that 'an ideal' learning environment for key competences should have (at least) the following features:

- The development of competences is based on active and experimental learning, where learners' individual development and personalised learning is supported. This implies more individualised approaches to learning that build on learners preferred learning styles and processes and improve students' motivation for lifelong learning.
- Teaching and learning with subjects and cross-curricular elements are well coordinated and teachers collaborate effectively. Teachers and students have time and space for cooperation. Each member of a school community has a clear understanding of how the development of key competences can be supported within subjects, and/or several subjects, and which ones require a completely new and different organisation within schools. It also requires pupil assessment to follow that logic⁸.
- This, in turn, calls for leadership that builds on a common vision of school development, and a shared/ distributed approach that encourages teachers to work in teams rather than only alone. Obviously, this approach would require support and recognition of teachers' professional development that is closely connected to school development.

To conclude the ideas exposed in previous paragraphs show that combining the competence-based approach with the traditional organisation of learning in schools poses a challenge that needs to be addressed.

The quality of learning material is crucial in supporting pedagogical approaches that focus on the development of key competences⁹.

2.3 STEAM LESSONS¹⁰

The main outcome of this deliverable is to characterize the 4 STEAM Lessons created within the project to make students concern about waste management and raise awareness mainly regarding prevention actions.

⁸ The PLAs have highlighted the importance of pupil assessment as an integral part of learning; looking into this issue will be one of the future priorities of the Cluster.

⁹ EDUCATION AND TRAINING 2010 WORK PROGRAMME (2008)- Cluster Key Competences – Curriculum Reform Synthesis Report on Peer Learning Activities in 2007 - http://ec.europa.eu/dgs/education_culture/repository/education/policy/school/doc/peer07_en.pdf

¹⁰ Further information about what STEAM lessons are is available at - A. ANNEX I - STEAM EDUCATION – SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY, ENGINEERING ARTS AND MATHS –DEFINITION

Each STEAM lesson in Waste4Think is defined to be used independently, has a beginning and an end and seeks to meet a series of specific objectives. In each material contents and competences will be trained together but they could be evaluated independently.

At the same time, as all the elements are connected and designed with a common objective, their joint use will allow the better achievement of envisaged objectives and the acquisition of more complex skills and knowledge.

The 4 STEAM Lessons that are the project outcome are teaching units that will be available in the following languages: English, Spanish and Greek.

2.3.1 Objectives

The aim of the educational units is to make possible a bottom up strategy in which citizen and scholars are the main actors. These STEAM lessons provide the paths and methods for transmitting all the acquired knowledge to other societal layers.

D4.3 deals with the release of 4 **digital STEAM** lessons with their associated Digital Projects and activities. All these resources created along waste4Think will be accessible for public from the project web page - waste4think.eu/.

3 USER REQUIREMENTS

First, a meeting with the main responsible for the project from each institution participating was arranged to meet people participating in the project and the expectations of each institution - 6 meetings took place along the first 6 months of the project.

This way, working team was able to understand the specific characteristics of each centre (how they work, what methodology they use, who promotes the environmental projects...).

Along these meetings schools' representatives explained how they work with the waste management and other environmental projects, their difficulties and how they expect to involve the Waste4think outcomes in their ordinary praxis.

3.1 QUESTIONNAIRES

To understand the possibilities to improve waste management at council level, reduce waste generation and promote good habits for separating preventing and reusing waste, a specific questionnaire was prepared. The results allow focussing on those issues and expectations of most interest for each municipality, considering that there is no standard baseline for all the pilots (each pilot keeps certain timeline particularities).

The survey also pursued the aim of getting data of each school related the state of the art about five main critical aspect for a correct user requirement acquisition:

- Educational level
- Educational methodology
- ICT infrastructure
- Software, digital applications and standards for teaching
- Waste management, resources and people involved

For each topic, 3-4 questions are provided to further understand them.

The questionnaire generated is available in ANNEX II (in English).

The survey was sent to Zamudio and Halandri schools participating in the project.

3.2 MAIN CONCLUSIONS

The results and conclusions obtained from the questionnaire can be summarized as follows:

- Most of the schools have medium level of using ICT resources with PCs available for students.
- Most of schools use open-source and free applications or file storage applications in cloud.
- Regarding waste management:
 - o All of schools have knowledge and do some activities related to waste management.
 - o Any of schools has a systematic methodology regarding quality and quantity of waste management although they do some punctual actions.
 - o Principal waste management are:
 - Paper, documents, paperboard and containers
 - Garden waste and food waste. Only one school manages food waste because it has kitchen, others use catering services and they are not allowed to manage this (Even Though catering services also generate waste, it's much less (bones, food remaining ...)).
 - o All the schools have the priority of having a compost bin. The school that have a compost bin speak highlight the importance of do not using food waste for the compost in the school because of the bad smell, but this is just a subjective opinion of the schools interviewed.

Further information about the main outcomes of user requirements collected by questionnaires in schools participating in the project can be described as follows:

3.2.1 General data

Each centre provides different formative stages covering all levels involved in W4T pilots' schools. In more detail, primary education and baccalaureate are the formative stages with a greater number of students.

Figure 3. Pilot formative stages

Most of the schools use the methodology of working by project, scientific method and lectures. And the facilities available are very similar, highlighting the dining room as a space where more waste is generated, in addition to the common spaces (classroom, patio or school environment).

Figure 4. Pilot waste generating spaces

On the other hand, all the centres have a school garden, but it is not active in all cases, although there is a common interest in taking better advantage of it.

All these features are important to understand the school's current situation and expectations for the Educational contents to be developed along Waste4Think

3.2.2 Technology requirements

Regarding the technology infrastructure, all the centres in Zamudio have electronic devices (Computers or iPad) and Wi-Fi connection.

That's not the case in Halandri

In terms of digital tools used in school, almost all use Google Drive, most Open Source applications and web tools. iOS operating system is only used in 1 centre.

Most of the schools share a common interest in robotics and programming. In fact, most of them already work on these topics at the centre.

3.2.3 Starting level of waste management

All centres know what the management of solid waste assimilated to urban is and manage it, although in a study performed with Zamudio citizens, answers show up that people still get confused about solid waste and organic waste because both of them are thrown in the same bin.

In each centre, student or teacher are responsible for the separation of waste, by using the following resources:

Figure 5. Pilot waste separation resources

Although waste separation is carried out in most of the schools, it is not systematized in a proper way or there a significant gap in waste data collection. Nevertheless, the waste type generated are clearly known. The most common ones are paper, plastic and food.

On the other hand, most centres collect light, water and paper consumption data.

In all the centres activities related to the separation or waste management are carried out and have good acceptance. The centres propose the creation of activities for the infant, primary and secondary stages, with the participation of the students and the teaching staff.

Schools interest is to have the chance to face innovative way to deal with food waste and calculating how much food they throw away. The main outcomes of the questionnaire remark that all schools know what management of solid waste is. However, their key interest relies on how to manage it and perform related activities. For this purpose of global concern of what waste is, all schools oversee waste separation (students or teachers), mainly using basic facilities such as bins in the classroom and containers outside the centre (Only 1 compost available) but there is no specific proceed for waste management neither for data collection (only light, water and paper) although main types of waste generated are known (paper, plastic and Food).

The activities did in Zamudio to mid-2018, have been:

	Date	Short description	Target group
Z1 General Campaign	mar-17	Presentation	Zamudio citizens
	nov-16	Citizen Survey	Zamudio citizens
	may-17	1st Citizen Participation Meeting	Zamudio citizens and other Txorierrri mancommunity citizens
	jun-17	Citizen Science: mapping Zamudio's containers	FDeusto Researchers, Mancommunity Managers & Zamudio citizens
Z2 Education Centers actions	23/10/2017 - 31/10/2017	Candle workshop in Zamudios school	Zamudio citizenship, school students
Z3 Food waste prevention			
Z4 Commercial activities campaign			
Z5 Composting	01/09/2017-...	Delivery of a small composting plant	Zamudio School, Vizcaya School
	24/06/2017-...	Community composting plant	Zamudio large generators and citizens
Z6 PAYT	oct-17	2nd Citizen Participation Meeting	Zamudio citizens and other Txorierrri mancommunity citizens
	ene-18	3rd participation meeting (M20)	Zamudio citizens
	jun-17	Eco-Event: Lagatzu popular meal	People who take part (people who took part)
Z7 Zero waste ecosystems	21/08/2017-27/08/2017	Eco-Event: Zamudio's neighbourhood Festivals	People who take part (people who took part)
	oct-17	Eco-Event: Arimen gaba-Halloween	Zamudio citizens
	04/11/2017-05/11/2017	Eco-Event: Agricultural fair	Zamudio citizens and citizens of Biscay
Z8 Miscellanius	abr-17	Domestic Oil bottle delivery	Txorierrri citizens
	jul-17	Campaign for Responsible Consumption	The event attendees
	sep-17	Gero Arte Campaign	Zamudio, Sondika and Derio children
LAN party (parallel action)	22/07/2017-25/07/2017	Campaign for Waste and Food Waste Prevention and Responsible Consumption	LAN Party Attendees

Table 3. Activities performed in Zamudio until mid2018

These once were taught to contribute to Zamudio's non-technological strategies:

- General Campaign: these campaigns which are not focused in some specific issue.
- Education Centres actions: these actions which are focused in child's and students of Zamudio.
- Food waste prevention: these campaigns try to contribute to reduce food waste.
- Commercial activities campaign: these actions want to reduce waste generation and take good habits in citizens' and retailers' daily consumption.
- Composting: there actions have as aim the prevention of organic waste by using auto-composting or neighbourhood composting plants.
- PAYT: for second-mid of 2019, Zamudio town-hall will implement PAYT scheme. For that, it has been necessary some citizen participation actions, and it has foreseen the introduction of PAYT issues in schools.

Zero waste ecosystems: these actions want to reduce waste generation in popular festivals, meals... and some environments like schools, town hall and some business.

The main challenges to be overtaken by schools in the context of the project are:

- They are working in personal and citizen skills in waste management. For the school is very important to work not only with the students but also with families and with the community. They are working in a project to search the waste on the playground.
- They have small gardens and a small orchard. They use their own compost to grow the plants and vegetables.
- They have their own compost space. They make compost using garden waste. They don't use food waste because of the bad smell.
- To introduce the learning materials in different subject learning programs is expected to be a challenging point for teachers. Each teacher uses different learning methodologies and they usually are not motivated with environmental themes.
- Some of the initiatives they already tried are:
 - Basketball hoops for aluminium balls.

- Lost and found waste mural. Detective game.
- Give away or sell the compost they made in the school.

3.2.4 Proposed working themes

Almost all schools agree that they would like to work for projects (learning by doing) but unfortunately it is not feasible in an ordinary class.

The most and the less interesting points also come out with an almost unanimous answer from most schools participating - “Waste, programming and robotics” is the most interesting topic and “Waste and regulation” (and how to change current public regulations to allow more efficient and sustainable management systems) is the least interesting topic

Following school’s recommendations both in Zamudio and Halandri, the key working areas to be implemented in schools according to the questionnaire results selected were:

- Monitoring of waste generation
- Waste management hierarchy focus on prevention & reuse
- Waste source separation and recycling
- Food Waste
- Home Compost
- Product Life Cycle and environmental impact
- Waste taxes Pay as you through, waste invoice

Of course, the needs of each school are not the same, nevertheless there are some similarities between the priorities for Zamudio and some others in Halandri that we can summarized in the following table:

HALANDRI Pilot	ZAMUDIO Pilot
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring - Waste management - Food Waste - Home Compost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Waste separation and recycling - Monitoring of waste generation - Compost bin and food waste Other item is Product life cycle and environmental impact * Invoice and work in class – Specific issue for Zamudio council

Table 4. Content priorities by pilot

After further discussion with schools in Halandri and Zamudio once the questionnaire results were released and main contents agreed, the working team finally chose that the main ideas and themes each specific content should deal with, are the ones that appear in the following table. These specific contents and their associated themes will be further elaborate in the corresponding Digital Project.

CONTENT AND THEMES
<p>Monitoring of waste generation</p> <p>Which are they? How much Waste we do generate? Where? Why?</p> <p>Scientific knowledge about Monitoring way, Information as a base for decision making</p>
<p>Waste management hierarchy, focus on prevention & reuse</p> <p>The best residue is the one that is not generated,</p> <p>Prevention forms from design to use, reuse, repair, etc. Lifestyles and waste generation.</p>
<p>Waste separation and recycling</p> <p>Separate collection at source, the best starting point for a high quality and effective recycling</p> <p>The need to properly separate in origin to allow recycling, make the circular economy possible</p>
<p>Food Waste</p> <p>How much? Why? How can you give new outings? ... but not only at school ..</p>
<p>Home Compost</p> <p>Quality? Characteristics?</p>
<p>Product life cycle and environmental impact</p> <p>Concept of LCA, Ecodesign & Lifestyles</p>
<p>Waste taxes Pay as you through, waste invoice</p> <p>The true story of the economic cost of waste management</p>

Table 5. Content and themes of the learning materials

Once the contents were clarified, several presential and virtual meetings took place to further elaborate the Digital Projects and associated STEAM lessons. With schools in Zamudio, as the partner is located physically very closed to Virtualware headquarters most of the meeting took place presentially. Regarding Greek schools most of the meetings took placed virtually. The objective of these meetings hold was to come to a common understanding and shared

vision of the learning material conceptual evolution; to introduce, contrast and validate the digital project and STEAM lessons structure and ideas with schools' team; and decide the working methodology to be used in the class.

To achieve this goal, the following activities were performed:

- All the members had access to the materials and meeting minutes.
- During the materials development, all the advices, comments, and improvements were initially accepted, and 3 meetings took place to contrast and validate the final version.
- For mobile games design, Virtualware will prepare a questionnaire for the target group to capture the criteria and will do a workshop with a sample of the target group (although this task is outside the scope of STEAM Lessons release is included here as a next step in learning material development).
- All intermediate steps were temporary available at schools' working group repository to be revised and validate for the next meeting.

This methodology was checked against schools' expectations.

After all the work done, finally the outcome 4 STEAM lessons created were associated with two Digital Projects. The description of each Digital project and its linked STEAM lessons and Activities are described in following chapters.

4 ETHICAL ISSUES

The learning contents data capture procedures follow the ethical rules defined in WP9, the Informed Consent clause in case children are involved – as defined in D9.3 and data privacy rules for schools.

In this second case, privacy requirements for schools, the project is oriented to schools not to individual participants which requires a much lighter fact to fit to data protection regulation (i.e. if a Database would be generated with all the participants and their emails other warranties should have been incorporated – such as, rights to rectification and forgotten, information of what would happen with the data obtained at the end of the survey and contact email to exercise these rights)

The complete questionnaire is available at Annex II – Questionnaire, however below the informed Consents Clause as it is provided in the survey is shown.

The data protection information disclosure in the Information Sheets is generated based on general example and specific ones for pilots available at D9.5 – PODP – Requirement no. 6.

Informed Consent Clause.

Thank you for Reading this information

We would like you to participate in a survey about waste management habits within the Waste4Think project by filling this questionnaire. It is voluntary, but your answers will be of great value for the development of the educational materials that will be generated within the project.

We only need the e-mail of the school contact person to have a partner along the project. We do not need any further information; The questionnaire can be completed in an anonymous way. Although we will not be processing any identifying information, stored data will be treated in a way that ensures confidentiality.

The survey will be saved to know the evolution of the habits about waste management in educational centres along project life-time (4 years). The questionnaires will be stored in a Virtualware server in Basauri.

Personal data (such as e-mail of the responsible) will only be accessible for the research team.

The research results are part of a survey with the aim of improving waste management at council level, reducing waste generation and promoting good habits for separating, preventing

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and reusing waste. If you have any questions, you can contact Leire Armentia (larmenia@virtualwaregroup.com)

Do you agree in taking part in this survey? YES, NO, OTHER

I do confirm that I have read the consent clause and I accept the terms of use of data collected in the survey YES, NO

5 LEARNING MATERIALS

As previously mentioned along the deliverable the outcome learning materials to be developed in T4.2 are:

LEARNING MATERIAL	Number of Items
Digital project * ¹¹	6
STEAM Lessons * ¹²	4
Mobile games	4

Table 6. Work plan and delivery dates

Digital Projects provide the general framework that is directly linked to working areas identified in Chapter3 – User requirements.

STEAM lessons and Mobile games are specific contents that fit in this global approach about waste content educational process. Nevertheless, this task is not performed alone and is aligned with the whole project requirements, especially with T4.3 where specific sorting games are developed and can also be added in the Digital projects' framework.

To better clarify the relationship between Educational content selected, Digital Projects, STEAM lessons and mobile and serious games with the other outcomes of the project (Serious games and applications) the following matrix is provided:

In the matrix, can be easily seen that STEAM Lesson1 is associated with Digital project1 and STEAM Lessons 2, 3 and 4 are linked with Digital project 2 respectively.

¹¹ To manage agile way, it will be created the STEAM lessons inside of Digital project although it will be available through web site one by one

¹² To manage agile way, it will be created the STEAM lessons inside of Digital project although it will be available through web site one by one

	Educational Itinerary				Mobile Games				Serious Games				Apps			Other resources
	Educational contents				MB1. Calculate and compare the amount and type of waste you generate. Save a historical	MB2. Game Compost in RA? Take care of your virtual garden.	MB3. Waste factory Select and give them a new life.	MB4 RA Gymkhan a with real challenges	Ways2Sort	Ecodesign Game	Virtual City	Planning game	Citizen	Local Trade	Food waste	To be described
DP1 Prevention and reuse	ST0101															
DP2 Source separation and recycling	ST0201	ST0202	ST0203													
DP3 Home compost/Food waste																
DP4 Product Life Cycle																
DP5 Waste Tax																
DP6 Monitoring of waste generation																

Table 7. Matrix showing the relationship of the project outcomes (Serious Games, Learning Material & Apps) with Digital Projects

5.1 DIGITAL PROJECT 1

The STEAM Lessons developed are associated with the corresponding Digital Project, so first, the project itself is defined as the framework where the STEAM lesson fits. This definition has the minimum elements that are defined in this deliverable in section 2.2, and the ones defined and validated by the pilot schools.

DIGITAL PROJECT	
NUMBER	1
NAME	After the concert
AGE GROUP	Basic Education (primary and secondary)
MAIN SUBJECT	PREVENTION & WASTE RE-USABILITY
PROJECT DESCRIPTION	<p>Detective game.</p> <p>There is a big party at the village. You went down to the main square to participate in a theatre workshop that is organized in this time. When you arrive you find a lot of "garbage". The workshop has been cancelled. You and your group of friends have decided to investigate and solve this case.</p> <p>As the good detective you are, you should:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - analyse the "crime" scenario. - Collect clues and look for the guilty ones. - Identify how it could have been avoided. - Look for solutions. - Communicate what has happened to other citizens.
DURATION	6 H
RESOURCES	<p>Work scenario 1: Internet connection available: Internet connection, paper or PDF materials.</p> <p>Work scenario 2: There is no internet connection: Materials on paper, photocopies, cardboards, scissors, markers and glue.</p>
WORKING METHODOLOGY	WORK BY PROJECTS. INDUCTIVE THINKING. TEAM WORK. PROPOSE AN HYPOTHESIS, ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION OF RESULTS.
GENERAL OBJECTIVES	
SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Being able to search and correctly recognize the basic terminology on waste and its management. 2. Identifying people as the origin of the generation and management of urban solid waste (USW). 3. Acquiring the necessary knowledge for the correct identification and classification of USW. 4. Developing the analysis capacity to identify the necessary resources for the correct management of USW in your city. 5. Being able to devise, search, present, identify preventive measures that reduce waste.
GENERAL COMPETENCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Competence for verbal, non-verbal and digital communication. - Mathematics, Science and Technology. - Digital competence. - Initiative and entrepreneurial spirit. - Learn to learn.

<p>CONTENTS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Basic terminology on waste and its management. - Prevention measures in the generation of MSW. - Identification and classification of waste. - Identification of necessary resources for the management of RSU. - Appropriate waste management for the generation of quality resources - People as agents of change.
<p>CRITERIA OF EVALUATION TRANSVERSAL BASIC COMPETENCES</p>	<p>1. Communicating in a mother tongue and foreign language (EU). Competence for verbal, non-verbal communication.</p> <p>to. Know how to communicate</p> <p>b. Communicate, orally and in writing, with fluency, autonomy, creativity and effectiveness.</p> <p>c. Use, in an integrated and harmonious way, the basic codes of body language, arts and maths.</p> <p>d. Interpret, in a critical way, the socio-communicative reality of the society and the world and participate responsibly and with an ethical sense in the communicative processes of its context.</p> <p>2. Digital competence (EU). Competence for digital communication.</p> <p>a. Interpret and evaluate, in a critical way, the messages of the social media.</p> <p>b. Use ICT resources appropriately, effectively and responsibly, for designing and planning a task, managing information, creating digital productions, cooperating and communicating results.</p> <p>3. Learning to learn (EU). Competence to learn to learn and to think.</p> <p>c. Search select and record information from various sources (printed, oral, audiovisual, digital ...).</p> <p>d. Understand and memorize information (comprehensive thinking).</p> <p>e. Interpret and evaluate information (critical thinking).</p> <p>f. Create and select ideas (creative thinking)</p> <p>g. Use cognitive resources strategically, mobilizing and transferring learning to other situations.</p> <p>4. Social and civic competences (EU). Competences to live together.</p> <p>a. combining the satisfaction of their own and others' desires, assertively expressing their own feelings, thoughts and desires, while actively listening and taking into account the feelings, thoughts and desires of others.</p> <p>b. Learn and work in groups, assuming their responsibilities and acting cooperatively in the tasks of common objective, recognizing the richness of the diversity of people and opinions.</p> <p>c. Behaving in accordance with the ethical principles that derive from human rights and in accordance with social norms that derive from the basic social conventions for coexistence.</p> <p>d. Find a solution to conflicts, through dialogue and negotiation.</p> <p>5. Sense of initiative and entrepreneurship (EU). Competence for initiative and entrepreneurship.</p> <p>a. Generation of new ideas and solutions and suggesting alternatives to improve reality with a critical spirit, solidarity and from social responsibility.</p> <p>b. Execute the planned actions and adjust when necessary.</p> <p>c. Evaluate the actions carried out and make suggestions for improvement.</p> <p>Sources:</p> <p>* Heziberri_2020_c.pdf</p> <p>* GENERAL_STRUCTURE.xlsx (COMPETENCES tab)</p>

<p>EVALUATION CRITERIA. BASIC DISCIPLINARY COMPETENCES</p>	<p>1. Communicating in a mother tongue and foreign language (EU). Competence in linguistic and literary communication.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) including oral and written texts, in different supports, of different genre from the fields of use of interpersonal relationships, media, learning. Recognizing the global meaning and selects the information relevant to the proposed objective. b) Producing, in a guided way, oral or written texts, in different supports. Belonging to areas of use such as interpersonal relationships, media, learning. c) Participating in the interactive situations of the classroom and in the center, respecting the rules of communicative exchange. d) Using ICT in a guided manner in the recovery, selection, processing and communication of information to answer to the needs of the activity. <p>2. Mathematical, scientific and technological competence (EU). Mathematical competence</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Developing and cultivating appropriate personal attitudes inherent to the mathematical task in the search for solutions to research and problems. Identifying and posing simple problems of daily life that can be solved using different mathematical contents. b) Solving and formulating simple problems related to objects, facts and situations of daily life, selecting the operations and using the corresponding basic algorithms or other resolution procedures, including calculator, and orally expressing the process carried out. c) Solving open problematic situations and simple mathematical investigations and small work projects on numbers, calculations, measurements and geometry, using different strategies, collaborating <p>3. Mathematical, scientific and technological competence (EU). Scientific competence Natural Sciences.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Performing with the help of a script, research and field or laboratory practices applying the scientific methodology, assessing its execution and interpreting its results. b) Applying strategies of scientific work in the realization of tasks and projects. c) Using digital tools and Internet to manage information and create new content. d) Linking scientific ideas with technological advances and in other fields, recognizing that they allow an improvement in the quality of life. e) Suggesting, from examples of daily life, some of the main uses that people make of natural resources, pointing out advantages and disadvantages and making proposals for their conservation. <p>5. Mathematical, scientific and technological competence (EU). Technological competence Technology.</p>
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	<p>a) Accessing services for the exchange and publication of digital information under criteria of security, privacy and responsible use. b) Preparing and publishing contents on the web that integrate textual, numerical, sound and graphic information adequately.</p> <p>6. Social and civic competences (EU). Social and civic competence a) Obtaining relevant and concrete information about facts or phenomena previously delimited, using different sources, both direct and indirect. b) Developing responsibility, effort, perseverance and reflection on the learning process itself. c) Valorizing group work, showing attitudes of cooperation and responsible participation, accepting differences and tolerating the ideas and contributions of others in the dialogues and debates. d) Developing creativity and entrepreneurial spirit, increasing the capacities and competences to using multiple information to obtain innovative conclusions in different situations. e) Making a responsible use of nature's assets, contributing to preserving the environment by understanding and interpreting events, analyzing causes and predicting consequences.</p> <p>7. Cultural awareness and expression (EU). Consciousness and cultural expression a) Applying in visual and musical productions, techniques and resources appropriately to their own needs for expression and communication, arguing the reason for the choice.</p> <p>*EB_curriculo_completo.pdf *GENERAL_STRUCTURE.xlsx (COMPETENCES sheet)</p>
<p>EVALUATION METHODOLOGY</p>	<p>RULES FOR SELF-EVALUATION, INDIVIDUAL AND / OR GROUP EVALUATION.</p>

<p>STEAM Listed</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - STEAM 1 What has happened? <p><u>Hypothesis.</u> Analysis of a situation. Acquisition of knowledge in a targeted manner (basic concepts on urban waste).</p> <p><u>Description:</u> The village is having a great party. You go down to the main square to participate in the theatre workshops that are organized. When you arrive you find a lot of "garbage". The workshops have been cancelled. You and your group of friends have decided to investigate and solve this case DETECTIVE GAME What happened? Who has been responsible for this disaster? How can we prevent it from happening again? I work for groups of 3 people</p> <p><u>Associated subjects:</u> waste as a resource, planning and prevention, separation and management for the generation of quality resources.</p> - Material 2 ¿Could this situation have been avoided? <p><u>Prevention:</u> Analysis of the situation. Starting from data available, think and decide mechanisms to prevent this situation. How could it have been avoided? What resources are necessary? Exploration, resources to manage, ideas to reduce, quantify.</p> <p><u>Description:</u> Research team has compiled all the necessary clues, it seems that among them are the clear evidences of the crime and who the suspicious persons could be. How this situation could have been avoided? Work in groups of 3 people</p> <p><u>Associated concepts:</u> Prevention in waste generation.</p> - Material 3 How can we fix it? <p><u>Management.</u> The waste must be properly managed in order to recover the celebration in the main square.</p> <p><u>Description:</u> The research team, together with a neighbourhood group, separates waste and makes decisions about what to do with them. Will waste be thrown into the container? Will it be given a new life? Which are the main factors to take a decision?</p> <p><u>Associated concepts:</u> Waste separation, identification of necessary resources, resources vs waste ... quantification of generated waste.</p> - Material 4 How can we avoid it to happen again?
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	<p><u>Action.</u> Report what has happened, using real data from the researched performed and the measures taken is a good way to prevent it from happening again. Take a step forward for awareness. Create an awareness campaign for the agents identified as main key players.</p> <p><u>Associated Concepts:</u> Types of waste, prevention and management actions. Responsibilities</p>
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Table 8. Digital Project 1

5.1.1 STEAM LESSON 1 -Digital Project 1

STEAM 1	
TITLE	WHAT HAS HAPPENED?
DESCRIPTION	<p>The village is having a great party. You go down to the main square to participate in the theater workshops that are organized. When you arrive you find a lot of "garbage". The workshops have been canceled. You and your group of friends have decided to investigate and solve this case. DETECTIVE GAME What happened? Who was responsible of this disaster? How can we prevent it from happening again?</p>
TIME FRAME	50 MIN
RECURSOS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Digital / analog activity card (image and sections to be completed) - Dictionary- - Internet connection (recommended) to create the prevention campaign. - Cardboard, markers, glue and paper in case of not having internet connection or wanting to work offline.
WORKING METHODOLOGY	3 people working groups.
EVALUATION METHODOLOGY	Group evaluation template
OBJECTIVES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thinking over an event through a static image in time. - Being able to search and properly recognize the basic terminology about waste: garbage, waste, organic waste, inorganic waste ... - Being able to identify people and themselves as agents that generate waste. - Being able to classify the waste according to its typology.
COMPETENCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Competence for verbal, non-verbal and digital communication. - Mathematics, Science and Technology. - Digital competence. - Learn to learn.
CONTENTS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Waste concept versus resource. - Inorganic organic waste. - Waste classification. - Values. - Prevention in the generation of waste. - Hierarchy concept of priority: prevention and reuse, preparation for reusing, recycling - How to make an informative poster / video / podcast. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Meaningful search. o Use of content without copyright. o Use of digital tools for editing digital content (voki, canva, kizoa ...).
CREATION	<p>POSTER – “WANTED”.</p> <p>Including: two lines summary about what has happened. An image with tracks correctly named and classified and a second image with people in charge of.</p>

<p>ACTIVITIES</p>	<p>Activity 1. What has happened?</p> <p><u>Objectives:</u> Think about, discuss and conclude about the situation represented in an image.</p> <p><u>Content:</u> An image.</p> <p><u>Competences:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● competence for verbal, non-verbal and digital communication ● Competence to learn to learn and to think ● Competencies to live together ● Social and civic competence <p><u>Time Frame:</u> 15 minutes slot</p> <p><u>Action:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Shown up a situation based on an image - Think about what has happened. - Discussion about of each group's thoughts. - Debate and conclusions. <p><u>Conclusions:</u></p> <p><u>Result:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Oral presentation of a member of each group about the hypothesis of what happened. - Template with the first 2 sections completed.
	<p>Activity 2. Clues, what can found at the crime scene?</p> <p><u>Objectives:</u> Understanding and differentiation of waste and resource terms.</p> <p><u>Content:</u> the same image/material as Activity 1.</p> <p><u>Competencies:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Competence for verbal, non-verbal and digital communication ● Competence in linguistic and literary communication ● Competence to learn to learn and to think ● Technological competence <p><u>Time Frame:</u> 15 minutes slot</p> <p>5 minutes for searching. 10 minutes for discussion.</p> <p>Deepen in the terms definition according to different ages?</p>

	<p><u>Action:</u> Search for the meanings of the terms waste and Resource.</p> <p>Link the type of waste generated with the possible agents involved in the "crime".</p> <p><u>Result:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Definition of waste and resource with graphic examples. - File with the 3rd section completed.
	<p>Activity 3. Classification of the clues - Who made it?</p> <p><u>Objectives:</u></p> <p><u>Content:</u> Same material/image of Activity 1 and 2</p> <p><u>Competences:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Competence for verbal, non-verbal and digital communication ● Competence to learn to learn and to think ● Mathematical competence ● Scientific competence ● Consciousness and cultural expression <p><u>Time Frame:</u> 20 minutes slot</p> <p>10 minutes for group working in groups and 10 minutes for discussion all together.</p> <p><u>Action:</u> Identification and bunching of the elements appearing in the image according to the type of "waste" or "resource" and its characteristics.</p> <p>Link the type of waste with who was generated by and when</p> <p><u>Result:</u></p> <p>"Wanted" poster.</p> <p>In the poster the agents responsible for the situation must appear and a text as an awareness message. a list with the elements of the image classified according to each type.</p>

Table 9. STEAM Lesson 1

For each activity associated with this steam lesson a guide for teacher is provided with more detailed explanation for teachers about how to organise the work in schools and added in following points.

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D4.3

5.1.1.1 STEAM LESSON 1 – Activity Description

Steam 1 is composed of 3 activities with their associated guide for teachers. The three activities description is provided as follows:

5.1.1.1.1 STEAM LESSON 1 – Activity1

ACTIVITY 1	
Description	
<p>The village is having a great party but theatre workshops planned have cancelled. You go down to the main square and at your arrival, you find yourself surrounded by a lot of "waste", this is what the mayor was referring to. You and your group of friends have decided to investigate and solve this case.</p>	
<p>Section 1 What has happened?</p> <p>analyse what has happened and collect group conclusions in order to share them with the rest of the class.</p>	
<p>Section 2 Why it happened?</p> <p>analyse the reasons why this situation took place based on the information shown on the image.</p> <p>Who could have been the main responsible of this situation?</p>	

Table 10. STEAM lesson1 – Activity1

ACTIVITY 1 TEACHER'S TEMPLATE

INCLUDES EXPLANATION FOR PREPARATION OF THE ACTIVITY AND SOME EXTRA MATERIALS

METHODOLOGY:

The methodology of this activity is based on collaborative work, the observation and research about a scene to deepen into the concepts of prevention in waste generation and the awareness of participating groups about the concept of waste as a resource.

Steps to follow:

The day before the activity, you are recommended to watch videos 03, 04, 05. Once they have made section 2, Video 01 of Prevention is displayed. They are asked if they would change an answer or add something to their thoughts and they are oriented towards the possible solution.

On the day of the activity, create groups of 3 people. Present the image, the associated description text and the question (the image can be replaced by a photo of a town square with a similar problem). Give 10 minutes to analyse the image and 5 minutes for the group discussion and conclusions. Between all the groups decide one single answer to each question. Throughout the whole didactic unit each group will have a template like this and there will be a common file where the definitive answers will be filled in after being agreed by all the groups.

By default, the file must be used in digital format.

If this is not possible, if you are only using an activity, print the card of the selected activity.

If you are going to do the 4th, print the activity card 3.

Write it in the box and save it for the next activity.

The previous visualization of the following resources is suggested to be able better work concepts of prevention, reuse, recycling and waste as a resource.

01_PREVENTION: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JCq8I7hhSF0>

02_DON'T WASTE YOUR WASTE: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Kr_DGf77OhM

03_REDUCE: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=g3sOejrhquw>

04_REUTILIZA: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GXDRPpU2gaU>

05_RECICLA: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zM62QgO3RZQ&list=PL6TsQ7MR8Y07UoXnHF1htbrwI02vHDy0D>

Introduction to the activity:

Today we are going to play detectives. The municipality of XXX (use the name of the corresponding municipality) has asked us for help. Something has happened in the town square and we must help solve it.

The village is having a great party, but theatre workshops planned have cancelled.

You go down to the main square and at your arrival, you find yourself surrounded by a lot of "waste", this is what the mayor was referring to.

You and your group of friends have decided to investigate and solve this case.

Description

<p>Section 1 What has happened?</p> <p>analyse what has happened and collect group conclusions in order to share them with the rest of the class.</p>	<p>Solution: The main objective is to reach an agreement about a planned activity that generates waste / resources without prior dealing with this issue. The poster of the concert on the floor lets you know this situation. As it was a night event, people have taken dinner, snacks, bottles of drink, bags that now are scattered on the floor. Emphasis must be placed on how and when the waste has been generated. By Who? The conclusion must be to make aware that it is a responsibility of all citizens - starting by people in charge of planning the concert but also of those who attend.</p> <p>Each group must be able to identify the elements that generate waste, when and how they were generated and why.</p> <p>At the end of the discussion, the following questions will be asked:</p> <p>Are they waste or resources?</p> <p>Glossary: Terms to use (as described in D1.1 – Pilot Planning Documentation)</p> <p>Basic concepts for all ages.</p> <p>What is a waste? Something we do not want but has value, therefore a waste is a resource. Present video 02 https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Kr_DGf77OhM</p> <p>Organic Waste (quickly fermentable food waste, it gets decomposed and finally gets degraded) Experiment to put it in a box to see if gets fermented or not fermented ... Inorganic waste (something that lasts much longer).</p> <p>Food waste Glass Plastic bottles Container Paper and paperboard</p> <p>Concepts that can be added at higher levels of knowledge.</p> <p>Inert Residue Social actions Selective separation</p>
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<p>Section 2 Why it happened? Analyze the reasons why this situation took place based on the information shown on the image.</p> <p>Who could have been the main responsible of this situation?</p>	<p>Solution: The objective for each group to identify at least two reasons and 3 responsible person for the situation. Each group should be given free time to think independently about solutions and who can be responsible of them. If they do not have the capacity or have difficulty working autonomously, they can be guided by using 3 words for each question:</p> <p>At what time has it happened?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. During an event 2. Type of event 3. who is attending <p>Why it happened?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Type of products appearing 2. Interest of the people <p>Who has been responsible?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Type of waste 2. Who has organise the event 3 Specific persons <p>Possible solutions: Why it happened?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The concert has not been planned correctly, suggest not to carry waste. Example: "0 waste" concert, bring your reusable glass ... - There were not enough containers, the containers were full, they could not be opened .. People have decided to leave the waste outside - It is more comfortable to throw everything on the ground than to go to the container - People did not know where to throw each waste so they were finally thrown on the ground - ... <p>Who has been responsible?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All the people of the town, the managers of the event, those who have thrown it away, those who have not told them anything and those who have not done anything to pick it up.
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Table 11. STEAM Lesson1 – Activity 1 – Teacher’s guide

5.1.1.1.2 STEAM LESSON 1 – Activity 2

ACTIVITY 2	
Description	
<p>The village is having a great party but theatre workshops planned have cancelled. You go down to the main square and at your arrival, you find yourself surrounded by a lot of "waste", this is what the mayor was referring to. You and your group of friends have decided to investigate and solve this case.</p>	
<p>Section 1 What has happened? analyse what has happened and collect group conclusions in order to share them with the rest of the class.</p>	<p>(Write the answer agreed in the previous activity)</p>
<p>Section 2 Why it happened? analyse the reasons why this situation took place based on the information shown on the image and collect the main conclusions to share them with the rest of the class</p>	<p>(Write the answer agreed in the previous activity)</p>
<p>Section 3 What can be found in the crime scene? Select the elements of the image that should not be there. Group them by type and name each group. Share them with the rest of the class teams and create as many classifications as you think are necessary.</p>	

Table 12. STEAM Lesson1 – Activity 2

ACTIVITY 2

METHODOLOGY: Work in the same groups of 3 people you took part before.

Take 10 minutes to do the activity and 10 minutes for the discussion.

Between all the teams decide which classifications are valid and write them down in the space available for the third question. Preview video 02:02_DON'T WASTE YOUR WASTE: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Kr_DGf77OhM

Introduction to the activity: As an experienced researcher you must collect evidences on the crime scene. Put you on some gloves and select the elements of the image that should not be there, Which ones you think are suspicious? What draws your attention? Create groups with the selected elements and name them.

Template for teachers

The village is having a great party but theatre workshops planned have cancelled. You go down to the main square and at your arrival, you find yourself surrounded by a lot of "waste", this is what the mayor was referring to. You and your group of friends have decided to investigate and solve this case.

<p>Section 1 What has happened?</p> <p>analyse what has happened and collect group conclusions in order to share them with the rest of the class.</p>	<p>(Write the answer agreed in the previous activity)</p>
<p>Section 2 Why it happened?</p> <p>analyse the reasons why this situation took place based on the information shown on the image and collect the main conclusions to share them with the rest of the class</p>	<p>(Write the answer agreed in the previous activity)</p>

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<p>Section 3 What can be found in the crime scene? Select the elements of the image that should not be there.</p>	<p>Solution: Groups must identify the different types of waste Plastic waste Containers Food Waste Glass Waste paper</p>
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Table 13. STEAM Lesson 1 – Activity 2 – Teacher’s guide

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D4.3

5.1.1.1.3 STEAM LESSON 1 – Activity 3

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ACTIVITY 3	
Description	
<p>The village is having a great party but theatre workshops planned have cancelled. You go down to the main square and at your arrival, you find yourself surrounded by a lot of "waste", this is what the mayor was referring to. You and your group of friends have decided to investigate and solve this case.</p>	
<p>Section 1 What has happened? analyse what has happened and collect group conclusions to share them with the rest of the class.</p>	<p>(Write the answer agreed in the previous activity)</p>
<p>Section 2 Why it happened? analyse the reasons why this situation took place based on the information shown on the image and collect the main conclusions to share them with the rest of the class</p>	<p>(Write the answer agreed in the previous activity)</p>
<p>Section 3 What can be found in the crime scene? Find the elements that are part of the "waste" pile and make a list them all.</p>	<p>(Write the answer agreed in the previous activity)</p>
<p>Section 4 Classify the clues Classify the clues found. Which of them are waste? Which are resources? In which other way would you classify them?</p>	

Section 5 Who is responsible of this situation? Link the type of waste with who generated it and when.	
Section 6 Poster "Wanted" Create a poster with those responsible for the situation and with the elements that accuse them.	

Table 14. STEAM Lesson1 – Activity 3

An example about how the poster could be like;

THE SOLUTION
TO THE WASTE
MANAGEMENT
IS IN ALL OF
YOU!

Images from: pixabay.com & pexels.com

WANTED

FOR MEESING THE STREET WITH: PLASTIC,
PAPER, GLASS CONTAINERS, FOOD WASTE

WANTED Poster suggestion

ACTIVITY 3	
Template	
<p>METHODOLOGY: Create groups of 3 people. It's time to classify waste in groups. Each group presents its classification and choose which is the most appropriate. Other types of classification are shown and discuss who useful they can be. Use 10 minutes to create the classifications and put them in common. Use last 10 minutes to create a "Wanted" poster that includes the people responsible for the disaster and the evidences that accuse them.</p> <p>The visualization of these videos is suggested to raise the point about the best way to recycle beyond the classification done by colours:</p> <p>Classification by priority: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=s5J-DfWVxCQ Classification by type of waste: Biodegradable or inert: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EAQSlu2NLEs Classification by colours: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pH1CKLcqotU</p>	
<p>Introduction to the activity: You must inform the population of what has happened. Create a "Wanted" Poster with the photo of the responsible people and the evidence that accuse them. The first step is to classify waste to investigate who generated it. Once guilty people are discovered, create the poster and share it along your school, city or social network. Awareness of the problem is the first step towards the solution.</p>	
<p>Section 1 What has happened? analyse what has happened and collect group conclusions to share them with the rest of the class.</p>	<p>(Write the answer agreed in the previous activity)</p>
<p>Section 2 Why it happened? analyse the reasons why this situation took place based on the information shown on the image and collect the main conclusions to share them with the rest of the class</p>	<p>(Write the answer agreed in the previous activity)</p>
<p>Section 3 What can be found in the crime scene? Find the elements that are part of the "waste" pile and make a list them all.</p>	<p>(Write the answer agreed in the previous activity)</p>

<p>Section 4 Classify the clues Classify the clues found. Which of them are waste? Which are resources? In which other way would you classify them?</p>	<p>Classification by type of waste (according to the classification of the type of management in your municipality) colours: Level 1 Brown container: food and plants remaining Yellow container: Packaging (plastic, aluminium, tetra bricks) Blue container: Paper and cardboard Green container: Glass Rest</p> <p>Classification by composition: Level 2 Organic waste: food, plants, pruning, etc. Inorganic waste: Plastics, glass, aluminium packaging, paper (It gets degraded but takes a long time, dry humid).</p> <p>Other interesting terms for higher levels of learning: Classification according to their behaviour: Level 3 Inert waste / non-biodegradable waste. Biodegradable paper waste, food scraps, vegetable or animal origin.</p>
<p>Section 5 Who is responsible of this situation? Link the type of waste with who generated it and when.</p>	<p>Identify the guilty people and look for a photo or an image that shows the identity of this persons. Has only been one person or several people? There is no fixed answer. The goal is to realize that the waste has been generated and thrown to the ground by people of any age (cans of soft drinks, packages of potatoes, sandwiches ...) and gender or origin. They could have been even themselves. Add an image of those responsible for each team.</p>

<p>Section 6 Poster "Wanted" Create a poster with those responsible for the situation and with the elements that accuse them.</p>	<p>Solution: Create a poster, informing about what has happened and showing who the responsible people are. It is time to inform all the citizens about what happened. Here you will find an example of a poster where just by changing images and fill-in in the available clues you will be able to create your own "Wanted" Poster.</p> <p>Canvas: https://www.canva.com/ Link to a canva project: https://www.canva.com/design/DAC0m7pOhD8/share?role=EDITOR&token=-NZP6hYA8eDwWifwq9RiPA&utm_content=DAC0m7pOhD8&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link&utm_source=sharebutton</p> <p>Befunky: https://www.befunky.com</p>
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Table 15. STEAM Lesson1 – Activity 3 – Teacher’s guide

5.1.1.2 EVALUATION CRITERIA

WHAT HAVE YOU LEARNT?			
CONTENTS & COMPETENCES	Totally agree	I agree	I Disagree
We know that waste is a resource that has a value			
We know how to classify waste			
We can identify when and how waste has been generated			
We can list and classify waste according to some of its features			
We can measure the amount of waste using an image			
We can link objects, their characteristics and the type of waste			
We know what an organic waste is			
We know what an inorganic waste is			
We know what an inert waste is			
We know what a biodegradable waste is			
GROUP WORK	Totally agree	I agree	I Disagree
We have created a team			
We have put a name to the team			
We have shared the work equally			
We have participated all the people fairly			
We were able to reach an agreement when different opinions raised.			
We have helped our group partners when it has been necessary			

If we had a problem, we tried to solve it			
If we have not been able to solve it, we have asked the tutor for help			
USE OF ORAL AND WRITTEN LANGUAGE	Totally agree	I agree	I Disagree
We have spoken clearly respecting available time and in the requested language			
The texts created have no spelling mistakes			
We have used commas and punctuation marks correctly			
We have used capital letters at the beginning			
We have look for words that we did not understand			
We have used at least one new word throughout the activity			
USE OF TECHNOLOGY	Totally agree	I agree	I Disagree
We have used internet images correctly (free images or quitting authorship)			
We have surf in internet searching information about waste			
We have verified the sources of information and validate the contents shown.			
We have used digital tools to create the poster			

What would you improve in your next group activity? Free space for suggestions

Table 16. STEAM Lesson1 – DP1 – Evaluation template

5.2 DIGITAL PROJECT 2

This Project objective is related with the Schools Campaign and activities (Z2) described in D4.1 (section 5.2):

Improve selective collection and prevention teaching how to classify the waste correctly, identify waste as a resource, etc. Virtualware will propose a specific learning

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material, while the municipality will foster actions related to the monitoring of the collection and generation, by making characterizations of the school bins (made by themselves). The main objective of it is to find out which items they throw away in the school and know if they are doing well. The sorting game will be used after this among the students. These actions are proposed for the second and third trimester of 17/18 school year. To know better how they are doing nowadays, municipality will start asking schools about their good habits works in this subject (baseline) via surveys.

DIGITAL PROJECT	
PROJECT NUMBER	2
NAME	Where is Wastey?
MAIN SUBJECT	WASTE SEPARATION AND RECYCLING
AGE GROUP	Basic Education (Primary and Secondary)
PROJECT DESCRIPTION	<p>Looking for the Treasure. You have just arrived at your class-room and realized that the trash can is overturned and there are remains of food on the floor. It seems that an animal has entered in the class. You and your group of friends have decided to investigate and look for it. As a highly skilled researcher, you must;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - analyse the scenario. - Collect tracks. - Identify how it could have been avoided. - Look for solutions. - -Share/Communicate what happened.
DURATION	6 H (splitted in 3 weeks' time)
RESOURCES	<p>Working scenario 1: Internet connection available: Internet connection, paper or PDF materials. Working scenario 2: No internet connection: paper materials, photocopies, cardboards, scissors, markers and glue or zeal.</p>
WORKING METHODOLOGY	WORK BY PROJECTS. INDUCTIVE THINKING. TEAM WORK. PROPOSE AN HYPOTHESIS, ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION OF RESULTS.
GENERAL OBJECTIVES	
SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Being able to search and correctly recognize accumulated resources in the classroom or school. 2. Identifying people as the origin of the generation and management of urban solid waste. 3. Acquiring the necessary knowledge for the correct identification and classification of USW at the origin, as a first step for further good quality recycling. 4. Internalize the concept of prioritization reducing, reusing and recycling. 5. Developing the capacity to analyse and extract data from generated / managed waste in an approximate manner. 6. Developing the analysis capacity of analyse to identify the necessary resources for the t management of USW in your city. 7. Being able to create ideas, search, present and identify preventive measures for waste reduction 8. Being able to identify the value of the resources generated in the classroom

GENERAL COMPETENCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Competence for verbal, non-verbal and digital communication.- Mathematics, Science and Technology.- Digital competence.- Initiative and entrepreneurial spirit.- Learn to learn
CONTENTS	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Introduction: What is food waste?- Monitoring of generated waste- Prevention measures in the generation of USW.- People as agents of change.

<p>CRITERIA OF EVALUATION TRANSVERSAL BASIC COMPETENCES</p>	<p>1. Communicating in a mother tongue and foreign language (EU). Competence for verbal, non-verbal communication.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Know how to communicate b. Communicate, orally and in writing, with fluency, autonomy, creativity and effectiveness. b. Use, in an integrated and harmonious way, the basic codes of body language, arts and maths. c. Interpret, in a critical way, the socio-communicative reality of the society and the world and participate responsibly and with an ethical sense in the communicative processes of its context. <p>2. Digital competence (EU). Competence for digital communication.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Interpret and evaluate, in a critical way, the messages of the social media. b. Use ICT resources appropriately, effectively and responsibly, for designing and planning a task, managing information, creating digital productions, cooperating and communicating results. <p>3. Learning to learn (EU). Competence to learn to learn and to think.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Search select and record information from various sources (printed, oral, audio-visual, digital ...). b. Understand and memorize information (comprehensive thinking). c. Interpret and evaluate information (critical thinking). d. Create and select ideas (creative thinking) e. Use cognitive resources strategically, mobilizing and transferring learning to other situations. <p>4. Social and civic competences (EU). Competences to live together.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. combining the satisfaction of their own and others' desires, assertively expressing their own feelings, thoughts and desires, while actively listening and considering the feelings, thoughts and desires of others. c. Learn and work in groups, assuming their responsibilities and acting cooperatively in the tasks of common objective, recognizing the richness of the diversity of people and opinions. d. Behaving in accordance with the ethical principles that derive from human rights and in accordance with social norms that derive from the basic social conventions for coexistence. e. Find a solution to conflicts, through dialogue and negotiation. <p>5. Sense of initiative and entrepreneurship (EU). Competence for initiative and entrepreneurship.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Generation of new ideas and solutions and suggesting alternatives to improve reality with a critical spirit, solidarity and from social responsibility. b. Execute the planned actions and adjust when necessary. c. Evaluate the actions carried out and make suggestions for improvement. d. <p>Sources: * Heziberri_2020_c.pdf * GENERAL_STRUCTURE.xlsx (COMPETENCES tab)</p>
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<p>EVALUATION CRITERIA BASIC DISCIPLINARY COMPETENCES</p>	<p>1. Communicating in a mother tongue and foreign language (EU). Competence in linguistic and literary communication.</p> <p>a) including oral and written texts, in different supports, of different genre from the fields of use of interpersonal relationships, media, learning. Recognizing the global meaning and selects the information relevant to the proposed objective.</p> <p>b) Producing, in a guided way, oral or written texts, in different supports. Belonging to areas of use such us interpersonal relationships, media, learning.</p> <p>c) Participating in the interactive situations of the classroom and in the center, respecting the rules of communicative exchange.</p> <p>d) Using ICT in a guided manner in the recovery, selection, processing and communication of information to answer to the needs of the activity.</p> <p>2. Mathematical, scientific and technological competence (EU). Mathematical competence</p> <p>a) Developing and cultivating appropriate personal attitudes inherent to the mathematical task in the search for solutions to research and problems. Identifying and posing simple problems of daily life that can be solved using different mathematical contents.</p> <p>b) Solving and formulating simple problems related to objects, facts and situations of daily life, selecting the operations and using the corresponding basic algorithms or other resolution procedures, including calculator, and orally expressing the process carried out.</p> <p>c) Solving open problematic situations and simple mathematical investigations and small work projects on numbers, calculations, measurements and geometry, using different strategies, collaborating</p> <p>3. Mathematical, scientific and technological competence (EU). Scientific competence Natural Sciences.</p> <p>a) Performing with the help of a script, research and field or laboratory practices applying the scientific methodology, assessing its execution and interpreting its results.</p> <p>b) Applying strategies of scientific work in the realization of tasks and projects.</p>
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	<p>c) Using digital tools and Internet to manage information and create new content.</p> <p>d) Linking scientific ideas with technological advances and in other fields, recognizing that they allow an improvement in the quality of life.</p> <p>e) Suggesting, from examples of daily life, some of the main uses that people make of natural resources, pointing out advantages and disadvantages and making proposals for their conservation.</p> <p>5. Mathematical, scientific and technological competence (EU). Technological competence Technology.</p> <p>a) Accessing services for the exchange and publication of digital information under criteria of security, privacy and responsible use.</p> <p>b) Preparing and publishing contents on the web that integrate textual, numerical, sound and graphic information adequately.</p> <p>6. Social and civic competences (EU). Social and civic competence</p> <p>a) Obtaining relevant and concrete information about facts or phenomena previously delimited, using different sources, both direct and indirect.</p> <p>b) Developing responsibility, effort, perseverance and reflection on the learning process itself.</p> <p>c) Valorizing group work, showing attitudes of cooperation and responsible participation, accepting differences and tolerating the ideas and contributions of others in the dialogues and debates.</p> <p>d) Developing creativity and entrepreneurial spirit, increasing the capacities and competences to using multiple information to obtain innovative conclusions in different situations.</p> <p>e) Making a responsible use of nature's assets, contributing to preserving the environment by understanding and interpreting events, analyzing causes and predicting consequences.</p> <p>7. Cultural awareness and expression (EU). Consciousness and cultural expression</p> <p>a) Applying in visual and musical productions, techniques and resources appropriately to their own needs for expression and communication, arguing the reason for the choice.</p>
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Deliverable
D4.3

	<p>*EB_curriculo_completo.pdf</p> <p>*GENERAL_STRUCTURE.xlsx (COMPETENCES sheet)</p>
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Deliverable
D4.3

EVALUATION METHODOLOGY	RULES FOR SELF-EVALUATION, INDIVIDUAL AND / OR GROUP EVALUATION.
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<p>STEAM Listed</p>	<p>1- STEAM 1 What has happened? Hypothesis. Analysis of a situation.</p> <p><u>Description:</u> You have arrived to your class-room and you realize that the trash can is overturned and there are remains of food on the floor. It seems like an animal has entered in. You and your group of friends have decided to investigate and look for the animal.</p> <p>LOOKING FOR THE TREASURE</p> <p>What has happened? Work in groups of 3 or 5 people Generate the hypothesis based on real data. Select the best method for data collection. Identify if a correct waste management is carried out or not.</p> <p>STEAM 2 How can the guilty being found? Data collection and processing: Where is the animal who made this disaster? What resources are necessary? Exploration, resources to manage, ideas to obtain data and quantify them. Resources to collect the method and being able to reproduce it.</p> <p>Description: It seems that the animal hides in the waste. We can not empty the bins and neither put your hand in them. The animal could be scared and get aggressive.</p> <p>We will have to find out where he is by getting information about which is the standard weigh of bins and if find out any change. How do we collect this data? What elements are needed? Remember to record, collect, write down and explain the method used. Work in groups of 3 or 5 people</p> <p>The idea is to think about how weight data can be collected (i.e. empty bins, filled up and so on, using different types of scales , sensors, etc..). Properly write down and explain the working process followed (data capture of each type of bin, use of spreadsheet, formulas, tables, units of measurement, generation forecast, etc.) and (video of the execution, documentation, presentation, others.).</p> <p>In addition, the hidden animal can be a stone or a heavy element decorated in certain way that moves along the different classrooms participating in the project following a pattern (every week is in a different classroom, but following a logical movemnet prefixed by teachers : i.e. even week in a even classroom and odd week in an odd one)</p>
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	<p>STEAM 3 Which information is shown by the clues? Conclusions and debate: Based on data obtained, get conclusions about generation in the classroom / hall / course. Where is waste generated? When is more / less waste generated? Which type of waste is generated? Is there valuable anything that cannot be reused?</p> <p>Work in groups of 3 - 5 people.</p> <p>As generation data are available, link them to concepts of prevention and reuse as well as separation at source for the correct waste recovery.</p> <p>Material 4 - Presentation of the working process followed and results discussion</p> <p>Action: Create a graphical/text material that shows up the global path and the results obtained. Suggest actions or commitments of each group to improve individual and classroom / or plant management.</p> <p>Work in groups of 3 or 5 people.</p> <p>Summarize in a presentation the method used, the tools and resources, the conclusions and suggest improvements.</p>
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Table 17. Digital Project 2

In this case, for helping teachers to better understand the concept of Digital Project2, a teacher's guide is provided associated for the whole Digital project;

Deliverable
D4.3

DP2 PREPARATION – TEACHER’S TEMPLATE

METHODOLOGY: Research, inductive thinking. Working by projects

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PREVIOUS WORK

WHICH MATTERS THE PROJECT IS RELATED WITH?

MATHEMATICS. Planning, measurements, monitoring, prediction, data capture, interpretation of data, conclusions, presentation and interpretation of tables and graphs.

LANGUAGE Terminology: hypothesis, food waste, types of waste, organic waste, inorganic. Create and write down instructions for research (Title of research, necessary tools, planning, methodology, results and conclusions). Presentation of the data through an audio-visual format (use of spoken and written language) or through a graphic format (only through graphic materials).

ENVIRONMENT. Separation and waste management, monitoring, introduction to scientific thinking. Introduction to the concept of food waste.

TECHNOLOGY. Creation of own materials using on-line tools. Use of spreadsheets Use of individual or collaborative text processors (Google forms, Google drive ...).

SETTING-UP OF WORKING GROUPS:

Preparing the activity.

Level 1: The teacher draws up the activity.

Level 2: A team formed by students (3 people) draws up the activity (choosing the pattern to be followed by the mouse and have bins ready every day for the activity). These people can be members of the school environment committee, volunteers, etc

Research team

At least 2 research teams.

They are in charge of making a hypothesis, planning the work methodology, collecting the data and coming up with the results. Each research team should be about 2 and 4 people.

TIME FRAME

3-4 SESSIONS IN CLASSROOM - depending on the duration of each session.
5 days for data capture.

People in charge of the activity will prepare the work to be done in class in advance. The session involves an initial activity, a period of one week for data collection and three final sessions of data analysis, showing data and conclusions.

It is very important that during that week school/classroom bins not be empty by the cleaning staff to avoid losing the mouse.

For this purpose, it's necessary to have the following elements in the classroom:

- Paper management bin inside the classroom or any bin placed inside the classroom (this way, it is easier to weigh and not generate too much dirtiness). All bins should have a similar size. To manage paper helps to keep quite a similar bin weight. An in this case, the weight of the mouse stand out and makes easier to find out weight changes and helps to make a decision.

- A stone or solid element with an approximate weight of 500gr, where eyes, tail, and ears are added simulating a mouse. This element will be hidden inside each bin (see instructions to create the mouse).
- Waste bins for the selection of waste, in the classroom, corridors or other school spaces. The ideal scenario is to use the classrooms of the same floor
- Scale for bin weighing.
- Paper and pen or portable digital device (tablet, mobile) with spreadsheet (i.e. google sheet or Excel) to record the temporary data.
- DinA3 sheet (physical or digital) to create a map with the location of the bins and for writing down when and where the mouse appears each day.
- **ADVANCED OPTION:** Place a camera that records and saves or streams the images. This option would be valid on day 4, 5 and 6. Only use one camera could be used and should be placed in the trash bin where the mouse is expected to be (see options about how to install a camera to save or broadcast images in streaming).

PREPARATION OF THE ACTIVITY

Every day the teacher or team responsible for being "Wastey" must prepare the corresponding bin (there can be 1 team in charge of creating wastey and of placing it in a different bin every day following a established pattern), .

- check that bins to be used have quite a similar weight.
- place "Wastey" in the corresponding bin.

This exercise that be used in mathematics or environment classes, as well as in the language one (given more emphasis to different topics, for example, in the language class the most important point to pay attention to will be the terminology used)

Day 1.

Preparation of the activity scene. The overturned paper bin will be placed. Inside among the papers, food waste could be seen (i.e., an apple, some cookies, a piece of bread ...).

Outside the bin some footprints simulating they belong to a mouse will appear (paint the path to generate them).

Day 2.

Level 1: The mouse will be placed in the paper bin of the classroom next door (the objective is to create a recognizable pattern. Depending on how the classrooms are arranged a more complex pattern can be generated - another factor to be considered are the level and abilities of the students to recognize patterns).

Level 2: The mouse will be placed two doors apart from the classroom of the group that is taking part in the activity.

Day 3.

Level 1: The wastebasket where the mouse was on Day 2 will appear overturned and footprinted. The mouse will be placed in the paper bin of the classroom next to the one of Day 2.

Level 2: The bin where the mouse was on Day 2 will appear overturned and footprinted. The mouse will be placed two doors classrooms away from day 2 working space.

Day 4.

Level 1: The wastebasket where the mouse was on Day 3 will appear overturned and footprinted. The mouse will be placed in the paper bin of the classroom next to the one of Day 3.

Level 2: The bin where the mouse was on Day 3 will appear overturned and footprinted. The mouse will be placed two doors classrooms away from Day 3 working space.

Day 5

Level 1: The wastebasket where the mouse was on Day 4 will appear overturned and footprinted. The mouse will be placed in the paper bin of the classroom next to the one of Day 4.

Level 2: The bin where the mouse was on Day 4 will appear overturned and footprinted. The mouse will be placed two doors classrooms away from Day 4 working space.

Day 6

Level 1 and Level 2 must find out which bin the mouse is and capture it.

Note: If there are not enough classrooms, the working class will be repeated. Not to change floor is recommended (to help create the map of the presence of the mouse). If there are special classrooms on the floor, they can be used (laboratory, crafts, etc.) as long as access to them is assured. If there are no paper bins in the classrooms and they can be used the ones at the corridor. If not, Bins of the classrooms will be used even though they are not paper bins.

RESEARCH

STEAM 1. DAY 1 (50 minute session in the classroom):

Statement of the problem. Working teams will be created and possible hypotheses will be considered. One single hypothesis will be validated or refused.

The main objective is to verify the hypothesis and capture the guilty of this disaster without harming it. The professor or team responsible for "Wastey" must clearly explain the rules to achieve the goal:

RULES

RULE 0: Each research team must have a name.

RULE 1: Starting 5 days data could only be taking without touching the items inside the bins. The animal who provoked this situation could be scared and disappear. It is very important to capture it this situation not to happen again.

RULE 2: The 6th Day may select a trash bin to capture the person responsible for the disaster.

RULE 3: Everything that is in the overturned bins should be properly recorded and measured (weight) to get clues about the mouse.

RULE 4: The results presented will only be valid if they are based on real data. The methodology used should be easily replicable.

DATA CAPTURE METHODOLOGY (not mention which type of animal is, it should be proposed by the working teams):

Use of a scale: All the bins must be weighed, the one with the mouse will have a greater weight.

<p>Waste characterization: analyse the waste that is in the bins. The one having food waste should be the one where the mouse is.</p> <p>Use of a camera to capture images of the guilty: This could be an extra method, it should only be allowed to be used twice in the investigation after the 3rd working day. Camera should be placed in a bin only once.</p> <p>DAY 2, 3, 4 and 5. They must be consecutive. If there is a weekend pause in the middle, you can play as 2 days have passed. Therefore, the pattern is followed and the mouse jumps two classrooms or keep it as if a single day had passed. Collection of weighing data, waste characterization and / or placement of cameras.</p> <p>STEAM 2. DAY 6 (50-minute slot in the classroom). Data analysis and capture of the rodent.</p> <p>STEAM 3. DAY 7 (50-minute session in the classroom). Data analysis to think about the way waste management and separation at source is performed. Consider if it is correct or not and possible improvement actions based on the concept of waste resource and prioritization in waste management (reduction, reuse, recycling).</p> <p>STEAM 4. DAY 8 (50-minute slot in the classroom). Making up a video, poster or podcast showing up the hypothesis, the methodological approach, the results and the conclusions. Wrapping up ideas to improve the performance of the classroom.</p> <p>NOTE: It is highly recommended to keep data/images to show each step of the investigation followed. It is also encouraged to show-up results using the Excel sheet or the generated graphs.</p>

Table 18. Digital Project 2 – Teacher's guide

Some extra material related with the basic ideas explain in this Digital project are provided in C. ANNEX III - EXTRA REFERENCES FOR DIGITAL PROJECT 2

Deliverable
D4.3

5.2.1 STEAM LESSON 1 – Digital Project2

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 688995
The dissemination of results herein reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

STEAM 1	
TITLE	WHAT HAS HAPPENED?
SUBJECT	WASTE SEPARATION, MONITORING
DESCRIPTION	<p>Description: You have arrived to your classroom and you realize that the trash can is overturned and there are remains of food Waste on the floor. It seems like an animal has entered in. You and your group of friends have decided to investigate and look for the animal.</p> <p>What has happened? Work in groups of 3 or 5 people</p>
TIME FRAME	80 MIN
RESOURCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Waste available at the classroom - Video/photo camera - If there is no video camera: Cardboard, markers, glue and paper - Computer with office tools - If there is no computer: paper rulers and crayons
WORKING METHODOLOGY	Work in groups of 3 or 5 people
EVALUATION METHODOLOGY	Group evaluation template.
OBJETIVOS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Think about an event analysing the scenario. - Make up a hypothesis - Discuss the different hypotheses generated - Be able to reach a consensus for the selection of a single hypothesis to be tested - Be able to suggest a replicable method that allows accepting or rejecting the hypothesis - Generate a planning for your research plan based on predefined guidelines - Identify waste management elements in the classrooms - Elaborate a data collection plan
COMPETENCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Competence for verbal, non-verbal and digital communication. - Mathematics, Science and Technology. - Digital competence. - Learn to learn.
CONTENTS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analysis of an image. - Recognition of waste types. - Selection of waste. - Values.
CREATION	<p>Description of the hypothesis. Set a hypothesis, written, drawn or by other audio-visual means.</p> <p>Work planning and waste management plan.</p>

<p>ACTIVITIES</p>	<p>Activity 1. What's happened? <u>Objectives:</u> Think about, debate and come up describing what has happened in the classroom.</p> <p><u>Content:</u> Based on a scene/photo about the current state of the classroom, generate a hypothesis about what has happened. Identification of waste types, identification of animals by their footprints. Use of reliable information on the Internet. See Annex Teaching activity.</p> <p><u>Materials:</u> Wastey Research Template. Wastey Footprint Identification Template.</p> <p><u>Competences:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Competence in verbal, non-verbal and digital communication ● Competence in learning to learn and thinking ● Living together skills ● Social and civic competence <p><u>Timing:</u> 20 minutes</p> <p>5 min to create working teams and set the problem to be solved.</p> <p>15 minutes discussion and hypothesis selection.</p> <p><u>Action:</u> Reflection on what has happened. Presentation of the results of each group. Discussion and conclusions.</p> <p><u>Conclusions:</u> That there is a hidden animal that feeds on waste.</p> <p><u>Result:</u> Oral presentation of 1 member of each group with the hypothesis of what happened.</p>
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	<p>Activity 2. The clues, why did this happen? How can the guilty be captured?</p> <p><u>Objectives:</u> To be able to map the waste generation systems of the classrooms. Develop the creativity to suggest methods for data collection and catch an animal.</p> <p><u>Content:</u> Select the clues to take into account: you cannot empty the bins nor put your hand in them, you must help the animal to go out from the bin alone.</p> <p><u>Materials:</u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Wastey Research Template2. Wastey Research Map3. Wastey Data Capture Template4. Wastey Research Rules5. Scale6. Gloves7. Webcam8. Computers or printer <p><u>Competences:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Competence in verbal, non-verbal and digital communication● Competence in linguistic and literary communication● Competence in learning to learn and thinking● Technological competence● Mathematical competence <p><u>Timing:</u> 60 minutes advanced level</p> <p>20 minutes to answer the questions by teams and share the results internally. 10 minutes to discuss the research method applied 30 minutes to prepare the research material and review it.</p> <p><u>Action:</u> Perform the search method outline and define the resources needed to apply it.</p> <p><u>Result:</u> Suggested method guidelines and planning of the research and resources to carry it out.</p>
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Table 19. DP2 – STEAM Lesson 1

DP2 PREPARATION – TEACHER’S TEMPLATE

METHODOLOGY: Research, inductive thinking. Working by projects

<p>Activity 1 What has happened? analyse what has happened, generates a hypothesis and select the methodology to be accepted or not.</p>	<p>Objective: To develop the ability to set a hypothesis based on a real-life situation.</p> <p>Hints to induce it: There is gnawed food in the bin (if this is the paper bin, much better), there are footprints of a small animal on the floor.</p> <p>Here you can find examples of mouse footprints: https://www.uv.es/zoobot/huellas/apodemus.html</p> <p>In this link there is a template and a website (to be used if internet connection is available) for the identification of mammal footprints. The objective is to use it as material to identify the animal: https://www.uv.es/zoobot/huellas/fichas.html</p> <p>See Mammal identification Template.</p> <p>Materials:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Wastey Fingerprint Identification Template (URL or Printed) 2. Wastey research template <p>Methodology and timing:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. 5 minutes. Create groups of 2 - 4 people. Raise the problem and describe the scene What has happened? Spread the footprint identification template or URL. 2. 10 minutes. Each group suggest a working hypothesis based on data collected. 3. 5 minutes group discussion and selection of a single hypothesis to work on. <p>Glossary: Terms to be used</p> <p>Basic concepts for all ages.</p> <p>Waste/resource Organic Waste Inorganic waste Waste sorting Reduction Re-use Recycling</p> <p>Concepts that can be added at higher levels of knowledge.</p> <p>Inert Waste Selective separation Hypothesis</p>
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Activity 2 Why did this happen? How can this situation be solved?
analyse the reasons why the mouse is in the classroom. How can it can be captured

Objective: To be able to map the waste generation systems of the classrooms. Develop the creativity thinking to suggest methods for data collection and catching an animal.

Materials:

1. Wastey Research Template
2. Wastey Research Map
3. Wastey Data Capture Template
4. Wastey Research Standards
5. Scale
6. Gloves
7. Webcam
8. Computers or printer

Methodology and timing.

Reflection through open and closed questions. Approach of the working methodology, preparation of the material and of the research groups.

First, 3 questions are asked to help select the method of data collection. Then explain the methodology and prepare the material. The time will depend a lot on the age of the group. For younger ages or lower levels, it is better to leave the material prepared in advanced for each team to verify it, for younger ages or more advanced levels it may be the working teams who prepare the material based on the examples provided.

1. Why was the animal there? Do you think the mouse is gone? Where he could be hiding? (5min) (work team)

The goal is to show them that the animal can be hidden in any bin of the classroom or in a place where there is food waste.

2. We only have one chance to catch him. To do this, it is necessary to know all the bins available in the classrooms. Identify which of them could have food waste and predict where it will be. The first step is to create a map of the classrooms indicating where the waste management bins are located. (10 min) (work team)

Share a wastey research map, tell them to open it on their device or to generate a map by hand. The provided Wastey research map is just a draft example that you will have to modify. On this map you should draw all the bins, indicate each one for which waste type is ready and give a different number to each of them.

3. Six days are available to catch the mouse and there is only one chance to catch it. If there are X bins in the whole plant, how can we know where the mouse is? It's time to create a research map. Think about which of these data can give us information about the presence of the mouse, and which can help us to predict where the sixth day will be. (5 min) (The whole group worked together). b, a and d must be selected.

	<p>a. There are traces. Footprints, gnawed food, excrement. (valid, observe and confirm the animal have gone this way)</p> <p>b. If the mouse is in the trash can, it's heavier. (valid only if all bins have the same content. It must be included in the research steps to characterize waste management in your school)</p> <p>c. It makes sounds. (It is not valid, they do not usually make noise, moreover, due to the noise of the centre is usually very difficult to check)</p> <p>d. We use a camera to record it (only for +13 years old or tutored by an adult). Valid although it is useful to check that the mouse is there at that moment, not to foresee where it will appear. There is only one camera, so you can only use it once a day.</p> <p>e. There's food in the bins. If we just leave a trash can with food, we can make it go there. It's hard to control all day that no one throws food in the rest of the garbage, but it might be an option.</p> <p>4. Delivery of the material for the research and explanation of the working methodology. (10 min explanation and 30 minutes preparation of the material). Review the hypothesis and research methods.</p> <p>We think there's a mouse in the classroom that feeds on the food in the garbage.</p> <p>We're going to investigate and gather data to try to capture it.</p> <p>We have six days to capture the mouse. The first five days data will be collected. On the 5th day all teams will come together to decide where the mouse is. On the sixth day the mouse will be catcher.</p> <p>To do this correctly, the data will be taken every day in the first 15 minutes of action (all teachers must know it to let students leave the classroom, each centre must choose the best time for the weighing). Each person in a team should be responsible for recording the data requested in the Wastey data template.</p> <p>Remember:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. You must have a well-designed bin map; each bin must have a number. In the research data template, you must write down the corresponding number for each bin. There must be as many bins on the template as the ones on the map. (This may be prepared in advance by the teacher).2. You must decide in the groups who will oversee collecting data every day.3. Everyday bins should be weight and write down which kind of waste each one has (just by observing them without touching).4. You must indicate in which bins there are traces of the mouse.5. You must collect the waste dispersed by the mouse and sort it out.6. If you have a webcam remember that you can only use it twice on the 5th and 6th day of the investigation.7. If you can, take pictures or videos of the working process. They will be useful for research reporting.
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	<p>Here you have all you need:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">- 1 Wastey research data template for each team (Excel, or printed table). Adapt it to the bins in your school.- A scale.- Some gloves.- A webcam if the image registration method has been selected. (Recording template for +13 years).- Template with the rules and steps of the research (Research methodology sheet).- Research template. <p>Remember, as only one scale and some gloves are available, everyday work should be properly distributed (one person will weigh the bins, another person if look for waste on the floor and pick it up properly with the gloves, the rest of the team will review which type of waste is in each bin and will record the data in the Data Template).</p> <p>Glossary of terms</p> <p>Food waste vs. organic waste (It is not the same. Food waste is part of biowaste more than organic waste) Selective separation (source separation/separate collection) Paper waste Plastic waste Prevention Reduction Re-use Recycling Waste/resource</p> <p>Possible solutions:</p> <p>Why did this happen? Someone has thrown food into the paper/plastic wastebasket. In addition, there are other wastes that should not be there, sort and place each waste where it should be</p> <p>Who is the guilty? How can be catches? Many capture methods may appear. There is only one chance to capture it so you must first guess which trash can it be from the different classrooms available and then capture it. To this end, 3 methods are proposed: o Level 1: Waste characterisation. Look for food residue in the bins. If there is food waste the mouse must have been there. o Level 2: Weighting method. The trash containing food waste weighs more than the others. o Level 3: Recording with a camera. If we know where it is we can record it (this option can only be done with students over 13 years old or managed by a teacher who will be the person registering the web recording system).</p>
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Table 20. DP2 – STEAM Lesson1 – Teacher’s guide

5.2.1.1 DP2 STEAM LESSON1 – Activity 1 Description

ACTIVITY 1	
Template	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Make sure you have both the research template and the footprint identification template with you - Complete the first 4 sections of the research template 	

Table 21. DP2 – STEAM Lesson 1 – Activity 1

5.2.1.2 DP2 STEAM LESSON1 – Activity 2 Description

ACTIVITY 2

Template

- - Make sure you have the - WASTEY research template
- - Fill in section 5

INVESTIGACIÓN WASTEY RESEARCH		
NAME OF THE RESEARCH TEAM		
NAME FOR PERSONS INVOLVED AND ASSOCIATED TASKS	NAME	TASK
WORK HYPOTHESIS		
SELECTED HYPOTHESIS		
METHODOLOGY (MAX 5 LINES)		
RESULTS <small>(Describe the data obtained and the results obtained)</small>		
CONCLUSIONS <small>(Describe the results obtained and the conclusions)</small>		

BE SURE YOU HAVE ALL THE MATERIALS YOU NEED TO START THE RESEARCH PROCESS

WASTEY research map. You will have to adapt it to your school (if you prefer you can draw it by hand).
WASTEY data capture template. (Adapt it to your school needs, 1 template by each classroom).

Table 22. DP2 – STEAM Lesson 1 – Activity 2

5.2.1.3 EVALUATION CRITERIA

WHAT HAVE YOU LEARNT?			
CONTENTS & COMPETENCES	Totally agree	I agree	I Disagree
We know the difference between waste and waste as a resource			
We know that it is a hypothesis			
We can make up a methodology for working			
We can plan a data collection			
We can place in a map the bins of our classroom and the closer ones in other classrooms			
We can identify what waste is thrown in each bin			
We can identify when waste is not in correctly thrown in the corresponding bin			
We can analyse footprints to identify an animal			
We can deduce a hypothesis starting from data			
GROUP WORK	Totally agree	I agree	I Disagree
We have created a team			
We have put a name to the team			
We have shared the work equally			
We have participated all the people fairly			
We were able to reach an agreement when different opinions raised.			
We have helped our group partners when it has been necessary			
If we had a problem, we tried to solve it			
If we have not been able to solve it, we have asked the tutor for help			
USE OF ORAL AND WRITTEN LANGUAGE	Totally agree	I agree	I Disagree
We have spoken clearly respecting available time and in the requested language			
The texts created have no spelling mistakes			
We have used commas and punctuation marks correctly			
We have used capital letters at the beginning			
We have look for words that we did not understand			
We have used at least one new word throughout the activity			
USE OF TECHNOLOGY	Totally agree	I agree	I Disagree
We have used internet images correctly (free images or quitting authorship)			
We have surf in internet searching for information from reliable sources			
We have verified the sources of information and validate the contents shown.			
We have used digital tools to create a video or podcast			

STEAM 02 – DP02	
TITLE	HOW CAN THE GUILTY BE FOUND?
DESCRIPTION	The animal seems is hiding in the waste. We have been 5 days collecting data. Are we able to predict where the mouse is? Which information is provided by available data? Do we need more information to validate the hypothesis? analyse the data and decide which trash to go for to catch the mouse.
SUBJECT	DATA ANALYSIS, PATTERN DETECTION
TIME FRAME	50 MIN
RESOURCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Waste available at the classroom - Video camera - If there is no video camera: Cardboard, markers, glue and paper - Computer with office tools - If there is no computer: paper rulers and crayons
WORKING METHODOLOGY	Work in groups of 3 or 5 people
EVALUATION METHODOLOGY	Group evaluation template.
OBJECTIVES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Think about the information provided by the data available - Measuring waste generation in the classroom/corridor/centre - Be able to identify a pattern - Be able to generate a method and explain how it is used
COMPETENCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Competence for verbal, non-verbal and digital communication. - Mathematics, Science and Technology. - Digital competence. - Learn to learn.
CONTENTS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data analysis. - Values. - Correct classification of waste.
CREATION	Research template section 6. Presentation of team results.

<p>ACTIVITIES</p>	<p>Activity 1. Data analysis <u>Objectives:</u> To develop the capacity to extract information from data collected</p> <p><u>Content:</u> Each team will have to collect all the data acquired during the 5 days training and analyse them. Data will be classified in: Data showing the presence of the mouse at school installations. Images showing the research process. Characterization of generated waste. Mouse capture test. In case of having used them, recorded data about the mouse presence.</p> <p><u>Competences:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Competence in verbal, non-verbal and digital communication ● Competence in learning to learn and thinking ● Technological competence ● Mathematical competence <p><u>Timing:</u> 30 minutes</p> <p><u>Action:</u> Data analysis. Answers to the questions posed. Identification of a pattern from data.</p> <p><u>Conclusions:</u> Available data made possible to detect where the mouse was. It's proven that data can provide valuable information.</p> <p><u>Result:</u> Answer to the 3 questions, pattern of the mouse movement.</p>
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	<p>Activity 2. Where's the mouse?</p> <p>Objectives: To be able to reach an agreement for decision making. Use a pattern to predict an event based on real data.</p> <p>Content: Wastey research data Template. Map of bins. Answers to the questions in Activity 1.</p> <p>Competences:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">● Competence in verbal, non-verbal and digital communication● Competence in linguistic and literary communication● Competence in learning to learn and thinking● Technological competence● Mathematical competence <p>Timing: 20 minutes</p> <p>Action: Decide as a team and among all the teams members where the mouse is located. Data analysis and presentation of results.</p> <p>Result: Identification of the bin where the mouse is located.</p>
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Table 24. DP2 – STEAM Lesson 2

STEAM 2	
TITLE	DATA HAVE SHOWN THE WAY TO GET TO WASTEY
DESCRIPTION	<p>The animal seems is hiding in the waste. We have been 5 days collecting data. Are we able to predict where the mouse is? Which information is provided by available data? Do we need more information to validate the hypothesis? analyse the data and decide which trash to go for to catch the mouse.</p>
PREPARATION	<p>This STEAM takes place on the 5th day of data capture.</p> <p>Along these 5 days, the team or person responsible for the mouse has moved it around every day following the indicated pattern, leaving the traces that ensure its presence in each bin where the mouse has been.</p> <p>On the other hand, the teams have been recording data.</p> <p>It's time to show these data, share the results and decide where to catch the mouse.</p>
TIME FRAME	50 MIN
RESOURCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Waste available at the classroom - Data collection template, map, research templates, images, etc. - Computer with office tools. If there is no computer: paper rulers and crayons for results discussion
WORKING METHODOLOGY	Work in groups of 3 or 5 people
EVALUATION METHODOLOGY	Group evaluation template.
OBJECTIVES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Think about the information provided by the data available - Measuring waste generation in the classroom/corridor/centre - Be able to identify a pattern - Be able to generate a method and explain how it is used
COMPETENCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Competence for verbal, non-verbal and digital communication. - Mathematics, Science and Technology. - Digital competence. - Learn to learn.
CONTENTS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data analysis. - Values. - Correct classification of waste.
CREATION	Research template section 6. Presentation of team results.

<p>ACTIVITIES</p> <p>Where is WASTEY 1?</p>	<p>Activity 1. Data analysis</p> <p><u>Objectives:</u> To develop the capacity to extract information from data collected</p> <p>Materials: Data acquired during the 5 days training. + Bin map</p> <p>Validate that data available can provide the following information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data showing the presence of the mouse at school installations. - Weighing data from the bins. - Characterization of generated waste. - Images showing the research process followed <p>Working methodology and timing:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Put the team together. They must pull out the data capture template must be available and the bin maps too. 2. 20 minutes. You must answer these 3 questions: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Have you identified which bin the mouse has been in every day? b. How did you identify the presence of the mouse? Traces, there are bins that are heavier than usual, ... c. Do you think there is a pattern that the mouse follows? Did you someday succeed guessing where the mouse would appear? 3. 10 minutes. Sharing the results of the answers and discussion. <p>Basic concepts for all ages:</p> <p>Data Selective classification Scientific method Food Residue Organic Waste Inorganic Residue</p> <p><u>Conclusions:</u> Available data made possible to predict where the mouse was.</p> <p>It has been validated that data can provide valuable information.</p> <p>A pattern has been detected.</p>
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<p>Activity 2 Where is WASTEY 2?</p>	<p>Objectives: To be able to reach an agreement about decision making. Use a pattern to predict an event based on real data.</p> <p>Materials:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Wastey research data template. 2. Bins map. 3. Answers to the questions in Activity 1. <p>Working methodology and timing.</p> <p>Open questions. All answers are valid if they are based on the data collected. The teacher should help them to recognize the pattern previously agreed.</p> <p>Based on data collected, can you decide which bin the mouse is in? All working teams together must decide which bin the mouse is in and check if we have used the correct data to guess it.</p> <p>You have 10 minutes to decide which bin the mouse is in (the decision must be based on collected data) and 10 minutes to decide among all the participants in which bin to look for it (only one option)</p> <p>Concepts Data Selective classification Hypothesis Disprove Scientific method Food Residue Organic Waste Inorganic Residue</p> <p>Results: On the sixth day, which bin the mouse will be in must be selected. There is only one chance to catch it.</p>
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Table 25. DP – STEAM Lesson 2 – Teacher’s guide

5.2.2.1 DP2 STEAM LESSON2 – Activity 1 Description

ACTIVITY 1
Template
<p>- Use the data collect at the Wastey Data Capture template and the map to answer the following questions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Have you been able to identify which is the bin the mouse has been in each day? b. How have you been able to identify the presence of the mouse? Traces followed, if there is any bin with more weight than the others ... c. Do you think there is a pattern the mouse follows? Have you ever been able to guess where the animal would appear?

Table 26. DP2 – STEAM Lesson 2 – Activity 1

5.2.2.2 DP2 STEAM LESSON2 – Activity 2 Description

ACTIVITY 2
Template
<p>- Write down in the map the bin where your team has decided to look for the mouse. - Write down in the map the bin in where the classroom has decided to look for the mouse.</p>

Table 27. DP2 – STEAM Lesson 2 – Activity 2

5.2.2.3 EVALUATION CRITERIA

WHAT HAVE YOU LEARNT?			
	Totally agree	I agree	I Disagree
CONTENTS & COMPETENCES			
We know the difference between waste and waste as a resource			
We can correctly classify the paper, plastic and other remaining			
We can differentiate what a food waste is			
We can identify a data			
We know how to extract information from the available data			
We know how to record the data along the time			
We know how to record the data with the correct measurement units			
We can identify an erroneous data			
We can make a hypothesis and validate or discard it			
We can plan actions in different time slots			
We are able to represent data at least 3 different ways			
We are able to identify what prevention, reduction, reuse and recycling are			
GROUP WORK	Totally agree	I agree	I Disagree
We have created a team			
We have put a name to the team			
We have shared the work equally			
We have participated all the people fairly			
We were able to reach an agreement when different opinions raised.			
We have helped our group partners when it has been necessary			

If we had a problem, we tried to solve it If we have not been able to solve it, we have asked the tutor for help We have improved any action included in the previous evaluation (only answer if you wrote any)			
USE OF ORAL AND WRITTEN LANGUAGE	Totally agree	I agree	I Disagree
We have spoken clearly respecting available time and in the requested language			
The texts created have no spelling mistakes			
We have used commas and punctuation marks correctly			
We have used capital letters at the beginning			
We have look for words that we did not understand			
We have used at least one new word throughout the activity			
USE OF TECHNOLOGY	Totally agree	I agree	I Disagree
We have used Google Drive, Excel or another format to collect the data obtained			
We have created graphs from the obtained data			
We have used a digital device to generate graphic material of the working process			
We have used tools to edit and integrate these images in the research template			
We have used a webcam to create a streaming video			
We have read and respected the terms of privacy and conditions of use.			
In the case of being under 13 years of age we have not used this option, or we have used it through an adult.			

What would you improve in your next group activity? Free space for suggestions

Table 28. DP2 – STEAM2 – Evaluation template

Deliverable
D4.3

5.2.3 STEAM LESSON 3 – Digital Project2

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 688995
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STEAM 3	
TITLE	Wastey blushes us WASTE, BINS AND GOOD PRACTICES
DESCRIPTION	<p>Waste management in schools is carried out in a wide variety of ways. It depends on the type of waste generated, the containers available for sorting, the cleaning service, etc. But even though the big effort spent if there is no real will and knowledge about how to deal with waste it will not be managed properly. In STEAM 1 and 2, data have been collected about the type of containers (bins) available in the classroom, the amount of waste generated and the classification of waste. Now is time to analyse the data available after the Wastey* research performed from another point of view and decide whether there is any improvement to be so waste management.</p> <p>Are there enough containers? Is it possible to sort all type of waste? Do you know how to classify them? How much waste is generated? Do you know the measures that could be used to reduce the amount of waste generated? Have you seen specific waste that could be reused?</p> <p><i>*If you don't know Wastey you can do the 2 previous STEAMs or work directly with the data available from your classroom (Identify the bins available, waste generated and analyse the improvement actions).</i></p>
SUBJECT	DATA ANALYSIS, WASTE MANAGEMENT
TIME FRAME	50 MIN
RESOURCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Research data (If STEAM 1 and 2 have been performed) - Classroom and floor waste (if STEAM 1 and 2 have not been carried out) - Camera, paper and pen for waste identification (If STEAM 1 and 2 have not been performed) - Link or template about proper waste management - Video camera - If there is no video camera available: Cardstock, markers, glue and paper - Computer or equipment with office automation tools - If there is no computer: sheets, rulers and crayons
WORKING METHODOLOGY	Work in groups of 3 or 4 people.
EVALUATION METHODOLOGY	Group evaluation template
OBJECTIVES	<p>Develop the capacity to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - think about how waste is managed in the classroom and in the study area (classroom floor), based on data available. - To know the 3Rs and think about the possibility of reducing, reusing or improving recycling in the classroom. - Identify good and bad practices - Identify responsibilities - Identify improvement actions-

COMPETENCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Competence in verbal, non-verbal and digital communication. - Mathematics, Science and Technology. - Digital competence. - Learning to learn.
CONTENTS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data analysis - 3 Rs - Recognition of waste types. - Selection of waste. - Best practices in 3R's - Values.
CREATION	Data presentation with visual material. Prezi, Google Drive presentations...
ACTIVITIES	<p>Activity 1. Wastey blushes us</p> <p><u>Objectives:</u> think about, debate and conclude about data collected in the research process</p> <p><u>Content:</u> Based on the data collected in the research, identify the type of waste management carried out in the classroom and plant. URL</p> <p><u>Competences:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Competence in verbal, non-verbal and digital communication ● Competence in learning to learn and thinking ● Living together skills ● Social and civic competence <p><u>Timing:</u> 50 minutes</p> <p>10 minutes for activity planning. Introducing the key questions. 30 minutes approach and hypothesis selection. Data analysis and results obtained. Improvement actions suggestion. 10 minutes for results discussion.</p> <p><u>Action:</u> Presentation of research data obtained. <u>Conclusions:</u> Waste is managed correctly or not. <u>Result:</u> Oral presentation of the whole group of the results obtained in the investigation.</p>

Table 29. DP2 – STEAM Lesson 3

STEAM 3	
TITLE	Wastey blushes us WASTE, BINS AND GOOD PRACTICES
DESCRIPTION	<p>Waste management in schools is carried out in a wide variety of ways. It depends on the type of waste generated, the containers available for sorting, the cleaning service, etc. But even though the big effort spent if there is no real will and knowledge about how to deal with waste it will not be managed properly. In STEAM 1 and 2, data have been collected about the type of containers (bins) available in the classroom, the amount of waste generated and the classification of waste. Now is time to analyse the data available after the Wastey* research performed from another point of view and decide whether there is any improvement to be so waste management.</p> <p>Are there enough containers? Is it possible to sort all type of waste? Do you know how to classify them? How much waste is generated? Do you know the measures that could be used to reduce the amount of waste generated? Have you seen specific waste that could be reused?</p> <p><i>*If you don't know Wastey you can do the 2 previous STEAMs or work directly with the data available from your classroom (Identify the bins available, waste generated and analyse the improvement actions)</i></p>
PREPARATION	<p>This Steam takes place after the action of catching Wastey. Data from the research should be collected. The analysis will focus on waste management data that has been indirectly collected in the Wastey search process.</p> <p><i>* If STEAM 1 and 2 have not been done, a prior analysis of the type of waste and bins available in the classroom should be made, Activity1 will add an extra question for this option.</i></p>
SUBJECT	DATA ANALYSIS, WASTE MANAGEMENT
TIME FRAME	50 MIN
RESOURCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Research data (If STEAM 1 and 2 have been performed) - Classroom and floor waste (if STEAM 1 and 2 have not been carried out) - Camera, paper and pen for waste identification (If STEAM 1 and 2 have not been performed) - Link or template about proper waste management - Video camera - If there is no video camera available: Cardstock, markers, glue and paper - Computer or equipment with office automation tools - If there is no computer: sheets, rulers and crayons <p>Recommended preview links https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JCq8I7hhSF0</p>
WORKING METHODOLOGY	<p>Work in groups of 3 or 4 people.</p> <p>The teacher should guide in the data analysis process to obtain relevant information. The students should come up with a conclusion on their own. Once conclusions are obtained, they must be synthesizing and display in a presentation or poster.</p> <p>If there has been a group in charge of managing Wastey (and this task has not been done by the teacher) they should be distributed among the different working teams.</p>
EVALUATION METHODOLOGY	Group evaluation Template

OBJECTIVE S	Develop the capacity to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - think about how waste is managed in the classroom and in the study area (classroom floor), based on data available. - To know the 3Rs and think about the possibility of reducing, reusing or improving recycling in the classroom. - Identify good and bad practices - Identify responsibilities Identify improvement actions-
COMPETENCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Competence in verbal, non-verbal and digital communication. - Mathematics, Science and Technology. - Digital competence. - Learning to learn.
CONTENTS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data analysis - 3 Rs - Recognition of waste types. - Selection of waste. - Best practices in 3R's - Values. <p>Remarkable references https://www.researchgate.net/publication/279914764_Manual_para_la_Gestion_de_Residuos_Solidos_en_la_Institucion_Educativa</p>
CREATION	Data presented through visual material. Prezi, Google Drive presentations...

<p>ACTIVITY 1</p> <p>Wastey blushes us</p>	<p>Objectives: think about, debate and conclude about data collected in the research process</p> <p>Resources and Materials:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wastey data capture template - Bin map - Research Template - 3 R's Template <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o URLs: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JCq817hhSF0 o <u>Zona de reciclado de residuos en el centro:</u> https://labiznagaecoescuela.wordpress.com/2015/04/08/la-clase-de-4o-prepara-las-cajas-para-separar-los-residuos/ o <u>¿Cómo reciclamos en el aula?</u> https://labiznagaecoescuela.wordpress.com/separamos/ o http://www.txorierribhi.com/2016-2017-berriak/delegatuberdeekinlaneanhasigara <p>Timing and methodology:</p> <p>50 minutes. Open-questions asked to drive the activity and complete the objectives fixed, have a vision about how waste is managed, decide whether it is correct or not and establish improvement actions.</p> <p>10 minutes. Activity approach. Video Viewing and Presentation of Guiding Questions.</p> <p>Now that the exercise is finished - Wastey has been caught or not (positive or negative result), let's have a look at the information provided by our little friend. For this purpose, we have to take the data must be pulled from the research and see if we can get some more relevant information.</p> <p>30 minutes. Development of the activity. Open the Wastey data capture template and answer the following questions (Wastey blushes us -template:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Where and when is waste generated? - What kind of waste is in the classroom? (Row 7 bins - indicate what type of waste each bin is for) - Most probably: Paper, cardboard, plastic and food waste. - They may also appear markers, batteries... - How many bins are there per classroom? Indicate the total number per classroom. From 1 to 5 - Which are the different types of bins in each classroom? Usually, bins for paper re-use, paper, plastic and the other types of recycling, . Boxes for pens and felt-tip pens, batteries or other kind of waste could appear. - analyse: Does the type of waste bin match the type of waste that is thrown into it? What is the residue that is most often out of place? Yes or no. It could be anyone. - Which type of waste bin generates the most waste? Check weights. - Based on observed waste, is there any type that you think is reusable or that could be stopped from being generated? (paper used only on one side, bottle caps, empty plastic bottles, aluminium...).
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do you think it is possible to improve the way of separating waste? - Do you think it is possible to reduce the amount of waste? - Who are the main responsible for this situation? - Wastey blushes us - Yes (if there are improvements in waste management) / no (if everything is managed correctly). - Why? How could waste management be improved? <p>10 minutes presentation of results. And conclusions. Each group should answer these questions: Wastey blushes us Data indicate that this statement is true or false (why?) Why is so important to properly separate at source? Highlight the importance of waste as a resource. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_EA6VL1Zj0s</p> <p>How could the management be improved? Who should be invited to participate in this improvement process?</p> <p><u>Possible solutions:</u></p> <p>Waste is properly managed. There are enough bins for each type of waste, Separation at origin is properly done. Improvement; reduce the amount (reuse and reduce). Identify improvements or good practices (use of reusable packaging for snacks, aluminium or glass bottles, unpackaged fruit. Using paper on both sides...)</p> <p>Waste is wrong managed. There are not enough bins for each type of waste, there are, but separation is not properly done. Corrective measures (creating spaces and containers to manage waste, creating posters make people understand where each type of waste should be thrown to....).</p> <p>Action: Presentation of the results provided by the data. Identification of improvement actions. Identification of responsible parties</p> <p><u>Conclusions:</u> Waste is managed correctly or not.</p> <p>Result: <u>Oral presentation of the whole working group of the results obtained in the investigation.</u></p>
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Table 30. DP2 – STEAM Lesson 3 – Teacher’s guide

5.2.3.1 DP2 STEAM LESSON3 – Activity 1 Description

ACTIVITY 1
Template
<p>Answer these 6 questions.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. What has happened?2. Who has participated or who is involved? The guilty one/s who performed the action3. When it happened? The moment when it has happened4. Where it happened? The place where it happened5. Why or What was it done for? The purpose of why it was made6. How it was done? The way it was performed <p>- Choose a headline and a subtitle for the news ("Waste is delightful for mice", "Waste vs Rodents" - "Mice come to the classroom" Please, notice that each headline puts the focus on a situation/fact To select your own headline, first think about the fact you want to highlight; In Research Process? in data collection?, in mice or in waste?).</p> <p>- Select from all the images and resources generated which are the one better shows the research process you have followed and show relevant information. Select at least 3 images, 3 elements showing data (table, graph, image ...) and 4 keywords.</p>

Table 31. DP2 – STEAM Lesson 3 – Activity 1

Introduction to the activity.

Information is the key basis for education, values or changes in life habits. You cannot want what you do not know, you cannot change a habit without a reason why. That is why we will use all the information collected to advertise the data collected about waste and the importance of waste generation at the school.

For this purpose, we will generate a news item the data collected throughout the investigation. The tips is to use the episode of the mouse to share two main concepts:

If a correct waste management is carried out in selected classrooms (or not)

News must be based on proven facts not on assumptions, rumours or opinions.

A series of questions will be made. A round of 2 minutes for each of them will be done to collect answer and afterwards, select the one that best fits to our case. That's why in this case is very important to provide a short answer.

Solutions:

- **What has happened?** The presence of food in the bins of the classrooms has bring the mouse to the classrooms. A research process has been carried out to catch the mouse feeding on waste from bins of the 3th floor. A research process has been followed to better understand why the waste initially collected in 3th floor bin, has appeared scattered throughout the classrooms. Using as excuse to justify the activity that on the third-floor classrooms a correct / incorrect waste management has been detected-
- **Who has participated or is involved?** The mouse as the main guilty of the dirtiness of the classrooms. People in charge of the research.
- **When has it happened?** The time when it has happened. A research process has been carried out over the last 2 weeks.
- **Where has it happened?** Include the centre and the affected classrooms
- **Why or What was it done for?** To ensure cleanliness in the classrooms. To identify who caused the dirtiness.
- **How has it been done?** Describe the methodology followed by the research process.
- **Choose a headline and a subtitle for the news** ("Waste is delightful for mice", "Waste vs Rodents" - "Mice come to the classroom"
Please, notice that each headline puts the focus on a situation/fact
To select your own headline, first think about the fact you want to highlight;
In Research Process? in data collection? in mice or in waste?).

HEADLINES.

Waste wins the battle.

A mouse discovers the wrong waste management process.

A rodent and the chaos of waste.

1 school, 4 classrooms and the right / wrong waste management process.

An opportunity for the planet. (The objective is to highlight the waste concept and use the mouse as an element to bring attention to the subject).

A research, a mouse and the chaos of waste.

SUBTITLE.

A research game discovers an opportunity to improve waste management on the 3rd floor of the school....

A mouse puts the school "in red" ...

Wrong waste management becomes an opportunity to improve the planet.

- **Select from all the images and resources generated which are the one better shows the research process you have followed and show relevant information.** Select at least 3 images, 3 elements showing data (table, graph, image ...) and 4 keywords.

The selected elements must provide key information.

Example: images bringing attention about chaos in waste selection, an image showing the moment the mouse is found by the research team. Graphs showing data about waste generated.

Table 32. DP2 – STEAM Lesson 3 – Activity 1 – Teacher’s guide

5.2.3.2 DP2 STEAM LESSON3 – Activity 2 Description

ACTIVITY 2
Template
<p>It's time to write down the news and make an advertise.</p> <p>PREPARE AND ADVERTISE THE NEWS.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Indicates what has happened. - Indicate how you know that mouse is the guilty one - Indicates the number of people participating in the investigation. - Indicates the methods used to collect data. - Indicate the results, how much and which type of waste has been identified? - Provide some solutions to avoid happen again. - Indicates some consequences of right waste classification. <p>Place the headline and subtitle identified in the activity 1 of STEAM2 and the above information in a post (use the school blog, write down on a text document (Google drive, Microsoft Word ...).</p> <p>Use Voki or another similar tool (mobile recorder, for example) to spread your news. Include the link in your post</p> <p>Enrich your news including links to mobile applications, games or internet sites that show how to make a correct waste selection.</p>

Table 33. DP2 – STEAM Lesson1 – Activity 2

ACTIVITY 2
<p>Template</p> <p>It's time to write down the news and make an advertise.</p> <p>PREPARE AND ADVERTISE THE NEWS.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Indicates what has happened. - Indicate how you know that mouse is the guilty one - Indicates the number of people participating in the investigation. - Indicates the methods used to collect data. - Indicate the results, how much and which type of waste has been identified? - Provide some solutions to avoid happen again. - Indicates some consequences of right waste classification. <p>Place the headline and subtitle identified in the activity 1 of STEAM2 and the above information in a post (use the school blog, write down n a text document (Google drive, Microsoft Word ...).</p> <p>Use Voki or another similar tool (mobile recorder, for example) to spread your news. Include the link in your post</p> <p>Enrich your news including links to mobile applications, games or internet sites that show how to make a correct waste selection.</p>

Table 34. DP2 – STEAM Lesson 1 – Activity 2 - Teacher's guide

5.2.3.3 EVALUATION CRITERIA

WHAT HAVE YOU LEARNT?			
CONTENTS & COMPETENCES	Totally agree	I agree	I Disagree
We know the difference between waste and waste as a resource			
We know how to classify waste			
We can list and classify waste according to some of its characteristics			
We can recognize the importance of correct separation at source			
We can link objects, their characteristics and the type of waste generated			
We know what an organic waste is			
We know what an inorganic waste is			
We know what an inert waste is			
We know what a biodegradable waste			
We know the importance of prevention and recycling and act accordingly			
GROUP WORK	Totally agree	I agree	I Disagree

Deliverable
D4.3

We have created a team			
We have put a name to the team			
We have shared the work equally			
We have participated all the people fairly			
We were able to reach an agreement when different opinions raised.			
We have helped our group partners when it has been necessary			
If we had a problem, we tried to solve it			
If we have not been able to solve it, we have asked the tutor for help			
USE OF ORAL AND WRITTEN LANGUAGE	Totally agree	I agree	I Disagree
We have spoken clearly respecting available time and in the requested language			
The texts created have no spelling mistakes			
We have used commas and punctuation marks correctly			
We have used capital letters at the beginning			
We have look for words that we did not understand			
We have used at least one new word throughout the activity			
USE OF TECHNOLOGY	Totally agree	I agree	I Disagree
We have used internet images correctly (free images or quitting authorship)			
We have surf in internet searching information about waste			
We have verified the sources of information and validate the contents shown.			
We have used digital tools to create the poster			
What would you improve in your next group activity? Free space for suggestions			

Table 35. DP2 – STEAM3 – Evaluation template

Deliverable
D4.3

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6 CONNECTION WITH FIWARE OF WASTE4THINK

The learning materials, as other elements of the project, relate to the FIWARE structure as shown in the architecture defined in D1.1 (Figure 11 Generic IoT communication architecture).

Figure 6. Generic IoT communication architecture

Each pilot school can use the data collected and get from the architecture to compare the main indicators (Generation, Collection, Treatment, etc.) in the schools with the ones of the municipality and obtain conclusion with the students. The specific data to use in the STEAM activities depends of the location, Halandri schools could use the ones reported by the system defined in D1.1 Figure 14 Conceptual architecture of Halandri and Zamudio the ones defined in D1.1 Figure 15 Conceptual architecture of Zamudio.

All learning materials generated during the project will be obviously related to the contents and deployment of the Environmental Education Program and its Social Actions. The integration of all ICT tools in the Social Strategies were kept in mind since the beginning of the definition of the Environmental Education Program. During the first part of the project, Social Actions have been innovative activities but without the use of ICT tools. While the eco-solutions are being thought and developed, and until they are ready to use, pilots are detecting and describing the use of the ICT solutions in the Environmental Education Program. The idea is to use them (and the new functionalities they allow) during the implementation of the foreseen actions as they are described in D4.1 (current version) and detect new opportunities to develop new social actions around them. This integration will be summarized in D4.2 and will be integrated in a new version of D4.1 Environmental Education Program.

Regarding the implementation of the STEAM lessons, as well for the rest of the digital materials, is especially relevant the link to the Social Actions developed (or under developing) in Zamudio and Halandri Pilot. There is a double link in this case; on one hand, the messages and activities students can receive in the municipality to promote a change in habits regarding food waste, light packaging prevention, PAYT, etc. usually received with their families and in an out-of-school context; on the other hand, the messages and changes “lived” in their schools, improving school waste generation and separate collection. STEAM lessons (and following digital projects) are consistent with both.

6.1 WASTE4THINK KEY PROJECT INDICATORS (KPI)

6.1.1 KPIs as input for STEAM Lessons

This General Key Project Indicators (KPIs) are an important information input for the learning material.

As mentioned in D2.9, for ensuring that the CEPM is effective, it is necessary to update Key Project Indicators (KPIs). These indicators act as a measurement tool for the responsible of municipal waste management or the business manager/entrepreneur/researcher to assess how well the CEPM service is doing in the context of a CE, allowing their companies/municipalities to estimate how advanced they are on their journey from linear to circular.

In the D1.3 Sustainable Assessment Models, the KPIs that the CEPM will use have been defined, as follows:

Generation (for each Waste Collection Circuit (WCC))	T.1.2 Annual generation rate (kg/inhab /year)
Collection (for each Waste Collection Circuit (WCC))	T.2.3 Total gross separate collection (%)

Treatment for each Waste Collection Circuit (WCC)	T.2.4 Total net separate collection (%)
	T.3.1 Primary waste destination (kg)
	T.3.2 Dry recyclables to primary destination (%)
	T.3.3 Organic recyclables to primary destination (%)
	T.3.4 Residual waste to primary destination (%)
	T.3.5 Destination recycling (DREC) (%)
GHG emissions (total)	E.1.1 net GHG emissions (kg CO2/ kg of waste) collection & treatment
Management costs (total)	C.1.2 Treatment gate fee (€/ton)
	C.1.3.1 Collection and Transport cost (€)
	C.1.3.2 Total waste management cost (€)
Social impact	S.2.1 Number of workers (n)

Table 36. D1.3 – Table 5 Circular Economy Module KPIs

These values obtained via Fiware are used as input data in the Learning materials (for example - in STEAM 4, school indicators are obtained as reference values to compare or to make calculations with). However, STEAM lessons are a paper-based material and therefore, will not be linked with Fiware platform automatically. The input data to work with in the STEAM lesson will be obtained from the public observatory web page (At this stage, the observatory is not launched yet), but the data of these KPIs in M1 and M2 is available at Deliverables D1.3 and D1.4.

At the same time, when these values are calculated, the incidence of the Learning materials will also be considered (as described in chapter 7 – Monitoring). For example, to measure if doing these activities influences school members and their family's behaviour or feed the system with the data obtained from the Learning materials use.

7 MONITORING

The learning materials have as output a set of defined KPI to measure their educational effectiveness. The educational Contents/ Learning material will also be input information for Fiware platform to indicate the results of the educational effectiveness of the material generated in each pilot site (Zamudio/Halandri).

A set of 9 output KPIs have been selected to measure the impact according to usability aspects of the Digital Materials (DIGITAL KPIs) and enhancing learning process (Educational KPIs) about waste management&recycling by using these materials.

DIGITAL KPI	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Easy to use - USE 2. Easy to install programs and add-ons - INSTALL 3. Didactic Versatility: modifiable, levels, adjustments and reports - VERSATIL 4. Running execution - EXECUTION
EDUCATIONAL KPI	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Didactic Effectiveness, easy to achieve of objectives - EFFECTIVENESS 6. Ability to Motivate - MOTIVATE 7. Adaptation of the contents to the target groups - TARGET 8. Promote self-learning - SELFLEARNING 9. Facilitate cooperative work - COOPERATIVE

Table 37. Educational KPIs

The entity structure of a single learning material entity as input data in Fiware platform would be:

- LM_ID (to identify the learning material object provided by an user)
- AGE_RANGE (text)
- STUDENT_INVOLVED (text)
- USE (number 1-5)
- INSTALL (number 1-5)
- VERSATIL (number 1-5)
- EXECUTION (number 1-5)
- EFFECTIVENESS (number 1-5)

Deliverable
D4.3

- MOTIVATE (number 1-5)
- TARGET (number 1-5)
- SELFLEARNING (number 1-5)
- COOPERATIVE (number 1-5)

A more detailed explanation of each KPIs selected is described below:

7.1 DIGITAL KPI

7.1.1 Easy to use

1.- EASY TO USE			
1 GENERAL DESCRIPTION			
VARIABLE	DIGITAL		
STAGE	OVERALL		
TYPE	INDIRECT		
2 CALCULATION METHODOLOGY			
DEFINITION	Easy to use refers to the facility to use Educational contents in Task 4.2 Learning materials by teachers and students		
FORMULA	Rate from 1 to 5. 1: low – 5 excellent		
STANDARDIZED METHODOLOGY	Questionnaire to teachers		
UNIT OF MEASURE	Subjective opinion		
PROCEDURE	The moment to measure is when the application is finished		
PERIODICITY	2 testing periods: - After first release - When the final version is ready.		
3 OBSERVATIONS			
PRELIMINARY INDICATORS	NA	PRELIMINARY INDICATORS	NA

It is compulsory to measure at least at the end of the period of app development

7.1.2 Easy to install programs and add-ons

2. EASY TO INSTALL PROGRAMS AND ADD-ONS			
1 GENERAL DESCRIPTION			
VARIABLE	DIGITAL		
STAGE	OVERALL		
TYPE	INDIRECT		
2 CALCULATION METHODOLOGY			
DEFINITION	Easy to install programs and add-ons refers to the facility to install educational contents in Task 4.2 Learning materials		
FORMULA	Rate from 1 to 5. 1: low – 5 excellent		
STANDARDIZED METHODOLOGY	Questionnaire to teachers		
UNIT OF MEASURE	Subjective opinion		
PROCEDURE	The moment to measure is when the application is finished		
PERIODICITY	2 testing periods: - After first release - When the final version is ready.		
3 OBSERVATIONS			
PRELIMINARY INDICATORS	NA	PRELIMINARY INDICATORS	NA
It is compulsory to measure at least at the end of the period of app development			

7.1.3 Didactic Versatility: modifiable, levels, adjustments and reports

3.- DIDACTIC VERSATILITY: MODIFIABLE, LEVELS, ADJUSTMENTS AND REPORTS

1 GENERAL DESCRIPTION	
VARIABLE	DIGITAL
STAGE	OVERALL
TYPE	INDIRECT
2 CALCULATION METHODOLOGY	
DEFINITION	“Didactic Versatility: modifiable, levels, adjustments and reports” refers to have Mobile location-based games in Task 4.2 Learning materials with options to adjust, report or modify didactic con
FORMULA	Rate from 1 to 5. 1: low – 5 excellent
STANDARDIZED METHODOLOGY	Questionnaire to teachers
UNIT OF MEASURE	Subjective opinion
PROCEDURE	The moment to measure is when the application is finished
PERIODICITY	2 testing periods: - After first release - When the final version is ready
3 OBSERVATIONS	
PRELIMINARY INDICATORS	.NA
PRELIMINARY INDICATORS	.NA
It is compulsory to measure at least at the end of the period of app development	

7.1.4 Running execution

4.- RUNNING EXECUTION	
1 GENERAL DESCRIPTION	
VARIABLE	DIGITAL
STAGE	OVERALL
TYPE	INDIRECT
2 CALCULATION METHODOLOGY	

DEFINITION	"Running execution" refers to have educational contents in Task 4.2 Learning materials without running exceptions.		
FORMULA	Rate from 1 to 5. 1: low – 5 excellent		
STANDARDIZED METHODOLOGY	Questionnaire to teachers		
UNIT OF MEASURE	Subjective opinion		
PROCEDURE	The moment to measure is when the application is finished		
PERIODICITY	2 testing periods: - After first release - When the final version is ready		
3 OBSERVATIONS			
PRELIMINARY INDICATORS	.NA	PRELIMINARY INDICATORS	.NA
It is compulsory to measure at least at the end of the period of app development			

7.2 EDUCATIONAL KPI

7.2.1 Didactic Effectiveness, easy to achieve of objectives

1.- DIDACTIC EFFECTIVENESS, EASY TO ACHIEVE OF OBJECTIVES	
1 GENERAL DESCRIPTION	
VARIABLE	EDUCATIONAL
STAGE	OVERALL
TYPE	INDIRECT
2 CALCULATION METHODOLOGY	
DEFINITION	"Didactic Effectiveness, easy to achieve of objectives" refers to measure the efficacy of the Educational contents generated in Task 4.2 Learning materials with properly didactic sessions.
FORMULA	Rate from 1 to 5.

	1: low – 5 excellent		
STANDARDIZED METHODOLOGY	Questionnaire to teachers		
UNIT OF MEASURE	Subjective opinion		
PROCEDURE	The moment to measure is when the application is finished		
PERIODICITY	2 testing periods: - After first release - When the final version is ready		
3 OBSERVATIONS			
PRELIMINARY INDICATORS	NA	PRELIMINARY INDICATORS	NA
It is compulsory to measure at least at the end of the period of app development			

7.2.2 Ability to Motivate

2.- ABILITY TO MOTIVATE	
1 GENERAL DESCRIPTION	
VARIABLE	EDUCATIONAL
STAGE	OVERALL
TYPE	INDIRECT
2 CALCULATION METHODOLOGY	
DEFINITION	“Ability to Motivate” refers to the “engainment” generated by the Educational content in Task 4.2 Learning materials.
FORMULA	Rate from 1 to 5. 1: low – 5 excellent
STANDARDIZED METHODOLOGY	Questionnaire to teachers
UNIT OF MEASURE	Subjective opinion
PROCEDURE	The moment to measure is when the application is finished
PERIODICITY	2 testing periods:

	- After first release		
	- When the final version is ready		
3 OBSERVATIONS			
PRELIMINARY INDICATORS	.NA	PRELIMINARY INDICATORS	.NA
It is compulsory to measure at least at the end of the period of app development			

7.2.3 Adaptation of the contents to the target groups

3.- ADAPTATION OF THE CONTENTS TO THE TARGET GROUPS			
1 GENERAL DESCRIPTION			
VARIABLE	EDUCATIONAL		
STAGE	OVERALL		
TYPE	INDIRECT		
2 CALCULATION METHODOLOGY			
DEFINITION	"Adaptation of the contents to the target groups of the contents" refers to have Educational content in Task 4.2 Learning materials with ability to adapt to the students age and level.		
FORMULA	Rate from 1 to 5. 1: low – 5 excellent		
STANDARDIZED METHODOLOGY	Questionnaire to teachers		
UNIT OF MEASURE	Subjective opinion		
PROCEDURE	The moment to measure is when the application is finished		
PERIODICITY	2 testing periods: - After first release - When the final version is ready		
3 OBSERVATIONS			
PRELIMINARY INDICATORS	.NA	PRELIMINARY INDICATORS	.NA
It is compulsory to measure at least at the end of the period of app development			

7.2.4 Promote self-learning

4.- PROMOTE SELF-LEARNING			
1 GENERAL DESCRIPTION			
VARIABLE	EDUCATIONAL		
STAGE	OVERALL		
TYPE	INDIRECT		
2 CALCULATION METHODOLOGY			
DEFINITION	"Promote self-learning" refers to have Educational content in Task 4.2 Learning materials and the option to perform the educational process on your own.		
FORMULA	Rate from 1 to 5. 1: low – 5 excellent		
STANDARDIZED METHODOLOGY	Questionnaire to teachers		
UNIT OF MEASURE	Subjective opinion		
PROCEDURE	The moment to measure is when the application is finished		
PERIODICITY	2 testing periods: - After first release - When the final version is ready		
3 OBSERVATIONS			
PRELIMINARY INDICATORS	.NA	PRELIMINARY INDICATORS	.NA
It is compulsory to measure at least at the end of the period of app development			

7.2.5 Facilitate cooperative work

5.- Facilitate cooperative work			
1 GENERAL DESCRIPTION			

VARIABLE	EDUCATIONAL		
STAGE	OVERALL		
TYPE	INDIRECT		
2 CALCULATION METHODOLOGY			
DEFINITION	“Facilitate cooperative work” refers to have Educational content Task 4.2 Learning materials that would require collaborative working with other students inside/outside the class.		
FORMULA	Rate from 1 to 5. 1: low – 5 excellent		
STANDARDIZED METHODOLOGY	Questionnaire to teachers		
UNIT OF MEASURE	Subjective opinion		
PROCEDURE	The moment to measure is when the application is finished		
PERIODICITY	2 testing periods: - After first release - When the final version is ready		
3 OBSERVATIONS			
PRELIMINARY INDICATORS	NA	PRELIMINARY INDICATORS	NA
It is compulsory to measure at least at the end of the period of app development			

7.3 EDUCATIONAL KPI measure survey

In the questionnaire, as starting points include some standard questions for categorization of participating profiles such as age or number of students. Regarding KPIs, STEAM Lessons, as a non-ICT material, only the set of Educational KPIs is considered to be included in the survey. However, a Digital KPI (easy to use) is also included but faced in a more general concept that pure ICT usability point of view.

In order to better clarify the relationship between KPIs and questions generated the following table is provided:

General information		
----------------------------	--	--

Deliverable
D4.3

1	Age	In what age range is used?
2	Amount of students	How many students are involved?

Digital KPI		survey question
1	Easy to use	Is it easy to use?
2	Easy to install programs and add-ons	
3	Didactic Versatility: modifiable, levels, adjustments and reports.	
4	Running execution	

Educational KPI		
1	Didactic Effectiveness, easy to achieve of objectives	Does it facilitate the achievement of the objectives?
2	Ability to Motivate	Can be used to motivate students?
3	Adaptation of the contents to the target groups	Has it been easy to adapt it to the age range where it was used?
4	Promote self-learning	Does it encourage self-learning?
5	Facilitate cooperative work	Does it facilitate cooperative work?

Table 38. Educational KPIs

As indicated before the missing questions are more related with pure ICT educational materials and will be discussed for Digital Projects and Mobile Games evaluation.

In a more formal way, an example of the survey to be filled-in by schools about each STEAM lesson to get the feedback about the effectiveness of the materials created is shown below.

Through this form we want you to give us your opinion about:

In what age range is used? *

- 1st Primary (6-7 years)
- 2nd Primary (7-8 years)
- 3rd Primary (8-9 years)
- 4th Primary (9 -10 years)
- 5th Primary (10- 11 years)
- 6th Primary (11-12 years)
- 1st E.S.O.
- 2nd E.S.O.
- 3rd E.S.O.

Deliverable
D4.3

How many students are involved? - 25-50 - 50-100 - More than 100
Is it easy to use? Very difficult 1 2 3 4 5 Very easy
Does it facilitate the achievement of the objectives? Very Little 1 2 3 4 5 A lot
Can be used to motivate students? Very little 1 2 3 4 5 A lot
Has it been easy to adapt it to the age range where it was used? Very difficult 1 2 3 4 5 Very easy
Does it encourage self-learning? Very little 1 2 3 4 5 A lot
Does it facilitate cooperative work? Very little 1 2 3 4 5 A lot

Table 39. STEAM Evaluation Template

In the following link the questionnaire shared with schools in Zamudio is available as example:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLScc8Nb_Ye8jk0jmrwGEEL28LH40rwGeW4s1Ss8TuNVWjTESDA/viewform

Evaluación STEAM 1

Mediante este formulario queremos que nos des tu opinión sobre la STEAM Lesson ¿Qué ha ocurrido? del proyecto digital Después del concierto.

**Required*

¿Qué ha ocurrido?

¿En qué franja de edad se ha utilizado? *

Figure 7. Example of evaluation questionnaire in Zamudio (In Spanish)

The effectiveness of STEAM lessons in selected pilots (Zamudio&Halandri) will be implemented and measured through the indicated KPIs in Waste4Think outcome platform.

8 NEXT STEPS

In this deliverable the main outcome is the description of the 4 STEAM Lessons as part of the learning material.

Further steps of the work to be performed with educational contents include the release of the remaining 4 Digital projects and the design and implementation of 4 Mobile games for educational purposes about waste management for students.

These further outcomes will be described in detail in D4.4 - Implementation of R8: Digital Learning Materials.

9 CONCLUSIONS

In this deliverable the expected 4 STEAM lessons are described. Aligned with STEAM Lessons the associated two first set of four digital projects (DP) are described - STEAM lesson1 is associated with Digital project1 and STEAM Lessons 2,3&4 are linked with Digital project2.

The learning materials described in the document can also be found at:

Materials	Scientix	OERCOMMONS
Digital project 1	http://www.scientix.eu/resources/details?resourceid=23044	https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/module/43658
STEAM 1	http://www.scientix.eu/resources/details?resourceid=23044	https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/module/43658
Digital project 2	http://www.scientix.eu/resources/details?resourceid=23045	https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/module/43659
STEAM 2	http://www.scientix.eu/resources/details?resourceid=23045	https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/module/43659
STEAM 3	http://www.scientix.eu/resources/details?resourceid=23045	https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/module/43659
STEAM 4	http://www.scientix.eu/resources/details?resourceid=23045	https://www.oercommons.org/courseware/module/43659

The STEAM lessons designed and developed are adapted to the requirements and needs of two pilots sites; Zamudio in Spain and Halandri in Greece with school children. Nevertheless, other pilots express their interest to be involved as observers in the process.

Pilots positively assesses the use of materials in the classroom and its adaptability to the particularities of each centre. However, more clear data about their use and effectiveness will come along the next scholar year.

ANNEX I - STEAM EDUCATION – SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY, ENGINEERING ARTS AND MATHS –DEFINITION

First, what is STEM?

STEM stands for science, technology, engineering, and math. These four symbols represent the different areas of STEM education¹³.

STEM is a curriculum based on the idea of educating students in these four specific disciplines — science, technology, engineering and mathematics — in an interdisciplinary and applied approach¹⁴. Rather than teach the four disciplines as separate and discrete subjects, STEM integrates them into a cohesive learning paradigm based on real-world applications emphasizing the application of knowledge to real-life situations.

A lesson or unit in a STEM class is typically based around finding a solution to a real-world problem and tends to emphasize project-based learning. A variation of STEM is STEAM, which includes an 'A' for art and design. The arts animate learning because they are inherently experiential and because of their potential to develop creative and critical thinking skills in students¹⁵. Artistic design is becoming an important part of STEM education since creativity is an essential part of innovation. Many STEM lessons involve building models and simulating situations. A good STEM lesson ensures that students understand the connection to the real world. This way, STEM learning materials evolve to STEAM lessons (STEM plus arts).

Blended learning

What separates STEAM from the traditional science and math education is the blended learning environment and showing students how the scientific method can be applied to everyday life. It teaches students computational thinking and focuses on the real-world applications of problem solving. As mentioned before, STEAM education begins while students are very young¹⁶:

Elementary school	STEAM education focuses on the introductory level STEAM courses, as well as awareness of the STEAM fields and occupations. This initial step provides standards-based structured inquiry-based and
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¹³ <https://study.com/academy/lesson/what-is-stem-education-definition-importance-standards.html>

¹⁴ <https://www.livescience.com/43296-what-is-stem-education.html>

¹⁵ Grant, J., & Patterson, D. (2016). Innovative arts programs require innovative partnerships: A case study of STEAM partnering between an art gallery and a natural history museum. *The Clearing House: A Journal of Educational Strategies, Issues and Ideas*, 89(4-5), 144-152.

¹⁶ <https://www.livescience.com/43296-what-is-stem-education.html>

	real-world problem-based learning, connecting all four of the STEAM subjects. The goal is to pique students' interest into them wanting to pursue the courses, not because they must. There is also an emphasis placed on bridging in-school and out-of-school STEAM learning opportunities.
Middle school	At this stage, the courses become more rigorous and challenging. Student awareness of STEAM fields and occupations is still pursued, as well as the academic requirements of such fields. Student exploration of STEAM related careers begins at this level.
High school	The program of study focuses on the application of the subjects in a challenging and rigorous manner. Courses and pathways are now available in STEAM fields and occupations, as well as preparation for post-secondary education and employment. More emphasis is placed on bridging in-school and out-of-school STEAM opportunities.

Table 40. STEAM Education classified by age

Each STEAM lesson in Waste4Think is defined to be used independently, has a beginning and an end and seeks to meet a series of specific objectives. In each material contents and competences will be trained together but they could be evaluated independently.

At the same time, as all the elements are connected and designed with a common objective, their joint use will allow the better achievement of envisaged objectives and the acquisition of more complex skills and knowledge.

The 4 STEAM Lessons that are the project outcome are teaching units that will be available in the following languages: English, Spanish and Greek.

Objectives

The aim of the educational units is to make possible a bottom up strategy in which citizen and scholars are the main actors. These STEAM lessons provide the paths and methods for transmitting all the acquired knowledge to other societal layers.

Methodology

Firstly, the methodology followed to build the STEAM lessons will be based on the Inquiry Based Learning and the 5E approach:

Inquiry-based learning (also enquiry-based learning in British English) is a form of active learning that starts by posing questions, problems or scenarios—rather than simply presenting

established facts or portraying a smooth path to knowledge. The process is often assisted by a facilitator. Inquirers will identify and research issues and questions to develop their knowledge or solutions. Inquiry-based learning includes problem-based learning and is generally used in small scale investigations and projects, as well as research¹⁷. The inquiry-based instruction is principally very closely related to the development and practice of thinking skills.¹⁸

Inquiry may be referred to as a technique that encourages students to discover or construct information by themselves instead of having teachers directly reveal the information (Uno, 1999)¹⁹. The implementation of inquiry has had a place in science classrooms for less than a century. Before 1900, most educators viewed science as a body of facts that students were to learn through memorization and direct instruction.

Inquiry is a multifaceted activity that involves making observations; posing questions; examining books and other sources of information to see what is already known; planning investigations; reviewing what is already known considering experimental evidence; using tools to gather, analyse, and interpret data; proposing answers, explanations, and predictions; and communicating the results.

This specific learning processes that people engage in during inquiry-learning include²⁰:

- Creating questions of their own
- Obtaining supporting evidence to answer the question(s)
- Explaining the evidence collected
- Connecting the explanation to the knowledge obtained from the investigative process
- Creating an argument and justification for the explanation

Inquiry learning involves developing questions, making observations, doing research to find out what information is already recorded, developing methods for experiments, developing

¹⁷ What is Inquiry Based Learning (EBL)? Centre for Excellence in Enquiry-Based Learning. University of Manchester. Retrieved October 2012

¹⁸ Dostál, J. (2015). Inquiry-based instruction: Concept, essence, importance and contribution. Olomouc: Palacký University, ISBN 978-80-244-4507-6, doi 10.5507/pdf.15.24445076

¹⁹ Uno, G. (1999). Handbook on teaching undergraduate science courses: A survival training manual. Independence, KY: Thomson Custom Publishing.

²⁰ Bell, T.; Urhahne, D.; Schanze, S.; Ploetzner, R. (2010). "Collaborative inquiry learning: Models, tools, and challenges". International Journal of Science Education. 3 (1): 349–377. Bibcode:2010IJSEd..32..349B. doi:10.1080/09500690802582241.

instruments for data collection, collecting, analysing, and interpreting data, outlining possible explanations and creating predictions for future study.

Levels

There are many different explanations for inquiry teaching and learning and the various levels of inquiry that can exist within those contexts. The article titled *The Many Levels of Inquiry* by Heather Banchi and Randy Bell (2008)²¹ clearly outlines four levels of inquiry.

Level 1: Confirmation Inquiry	The teacher has taught a particular science theme or topic. The teacher then develops questions and a procedure that guides students through an activity where the results are already known. This method is great to reinforce concepts taught and to introduce students into learning to follow procedures, collect and record data correctly and to confirm and deepen understandings.
Level 2: Structured Inquiry	The teacher provides the initial question and an outline of the procedure. Students are to formulate explanations of their findings through evaluating and analysing the data that they collect.
Level 3: Guided Inquiry	The teacher provides only the research question for the students. The students are responsible for designing and following their own procedures to test that question and then communicate their results and findings.
Level 4: Open/True Inquiry	Students formulate their own research question(s), design and follow through with a developed procedure, and communicate their findings and results. This type of inquiry is often seen in science fair contexts where students drive their own investigative questions.

Table 41. Inquiry Levels

Banchi and Bell (2008) explain that teachers should begin their inquiry instruction at the lower levels and work their way to open inquiry in order to effectively develop students' inquiry skills. Open inquiry activities are only successful if students are motivated by intrinsic interests and if they are equipped with the skills to conduct their own research study²².

²¹ National Institute for Health. (2005). *Doing Science: The Process of Science Inquiry*. http://science.education.nih.gov/supplements/nih6/inquiry/guide/info_process-a.htm

²² Yoon, H., Joung, Y. J., Kim, M. (2012). The challenges of science inquiry teaching for pre-service teachers in elementary classrooms: Difficulties on and under the scene. *Research in Science & Technological Education*, 42(3), 589–608.

Open/true inquiry learning

An important aspect of inquiry-based learning (and science) is the use of open learning, as evidence suggests that only utilizing lower level inquiry is not enough to develop critical and scientific thinking to the full potential^{23 24 25}. Open learning has no prescribed target or result that people must achieve. There is an emphasis on the individual manipulating information and creating meaning from a set of given materials or circumstances²⁶ In many conventional and structured learning environments, people are told what the outcome is expected to be, and then they are simply expected to 'confirm' or show evidence that this is the case.

Open learning has many benefits²⁷. It means students do not simply perform experiments in a routine like fashion but think about the results they collect and what they mean. With traditional non-open lessons there is a tendency for students to say that the experiment 'went wrong' when they collect results contrary to what they are told to expect. In open learning there are no wrong results, and students must evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the results they collect themselves and decide their value.

The implementation of inquiry-based teaching is a major theme in national science education²⁸. Inquiry needs to be a central strategy of all science curricula. Using a learning cycle approach in the classroom helps to facilitate inquiry practices because learning cycles focus on constructivist principles and emphasize the explanation and investigation of phenomena, the use of evidence to back up conclusions, and experimental design. Although there are several variations of learning cycles, the one that is highlighted as a method to support inquiry-based

²³ Berg, C A R; Bergendahl, V C B; Lundberg, B K S; Tibell, L A E (2003). "Benefiting from an open-ended experiment? A comparison of attitudes to, and outcomes of, an expository versus an open-inquiry version to the same experiment". *International Journal of Science Education*. 25 (3): 351–372. Bibcode:2003IJSEd..25..351B. doi:10.1080/09500690210145738

²⁴ Yen C F and Hunang S C (2001) Authentic learning about tree frogs by preservice biology teachers in an open-inquiry research settings. *Proc. Natl. Sci. Counc. ROC(D)* 11, 1–10.

²⁵ Zion, M.; Sadeh, I. (2007). "Curiosity and open inquiry learning". *Journal of Biological Education*. 41 (4): 162–168. doi:10.1080/00219266.2007.9656092.

²⁶ Hannafin, M., Land, S., Oliver, K. (1999). Open learning environments: Foundation, methods, and models. In C. M. Reigeluth (Ed.), *Instructional-design theories and models. A new paradigm of instructional theory Volume II* (pp. 115–140). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Inc.

²⁷ Zion, M.; Sadeh, I. (2007). "Curiosity and open inquiry learning". *Journal of Biological Education*. 41 (4): 162–168. doi:10.1080/00219266.2007.9656092.

²⁸ Duran, L. B., & Duran, E. (2004). *The 5E Instructional Model: A Learning Cycle Approach for Inquiry-Based Science Teaching*. *Science Education Review*, 3(2), 49-58.

teaching is the 5E Instructional Model (Bybee & Landes, 1990)²⁹. The use of this model in several science education professional development programs is also addressed.

With much research to support inquiry-based teaching and learning, many teachers are opting for this non-traditional teaching approach. The incorporation of learning cycles in the classroom aids teachers in the pursuit of the development of effective inquiry-based science lessons. The 5E Instructional Model serves as a flexible learning cycle that assists curriculum developers and classroom teachers create science lessons that illustrate constructivist, reform-based, best teaching practices.

The 5E approach is an instructional model based on the constructivist approach to learning, which says that learners build or construct new ideas on top of their old ideas³⁰. The 5 E's can be used with students of all ages, including adults.

Each of the 5 E's describes a phase of learning, and each phase begins with the letter "E": Engage, Explore, Explain, Elaborate, and Evaluate. The 5 E's allows students and teachers to experience common activities, to use and build on prior knowledge and experience, to construct meaning, and to continually assess their understanding of a concept upon cognitive psychology, constructivist-learning theory, and best practices in science teaching.

The cycle appears in the following figure and consists of cognitive stages of learning that comprise engage, explore, explain, elaborate, and evaluate. Bybee (1997)³¹ declares that "using this approach, students redefine, reorganize, elaborate, and change their initial concepts through self-reflection and interaction with their peers and their environment. Learners interpret objects and phenomena and internalize those interpretations in terms of their current conceptual understanding". Science teachers and curriculum developers may integrate or apply the model at several levels.

²⁹ Bybee, R., & Landes, N. M. (1990). Science for life and living: An elementary school science program from Biological Sciences Improvement Study (BSCS). *The American Biology Teacher*, 52(2), 92-98.

³⁰ <http://enhancinged.wgbh.org/research/eeeeee.html>

³¹ Bybee, R. (1997). *Achieving scientific literacy: From purposes to practices*. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann Publications.

Figure 8. The 5E instructional model

The model can be the organizing pattern of a sequence of daily lessons, individual units, or yearly plans (Bybee, 1997)³². Each phase of the 5E Instructional Learning Cycle, is now described:

Engage	<p>This phase of the 5 E's starts the process.</p> <p>In this first phase of the cycle, the teacher aims to assess student prior knowledge and/or identify possible misconceptions. This student-centered phase should be a motivational period that can create a desire to learn more about the upcoming topic. Students may brainstorm an opening question or ask themselves:</p> <p>“What do I already know about this topic?” Discrepant events, demonstrations, questioning, or graphic organizers may be included to create interest or generate curiosity. Students are asked to brainstorm and record what they Know, Want to know, and (eventually) have Learned about the topic in order to pre-assess student prior knowledge and is oftentimes referred to throughout the duration of the lesson. The instructional task is identified.</p> <p>However, this phase does not serve as a time to lecture, define terms, provide explanations, or record definitions.</p>
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³² Bybee, R. (1997). *Achieving scientific literacy: From purposes to practices*. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann Publications.

	<p>To conclude, an "engage" activity should do the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Make connections between past and present learning experiences ▪ Anticipate activities and focus students' thinking on the learning outcomes of current activities. Students should become mentally engaged in the concept, process, or skill to be learned.
Explore	<p>Following an engagement phase that promotes a mental focus on the concept, the exploration phase now provides the students with a common, concrete learning experience. This phase is also student-centered and incorporates active exploration. Students are encouraged to apply process skills, such as observing, questioning, investigating, testing predictions, hypothesizing, and communicating, with other peers. This phase of the learning cycle tends to incorporate the main inquiry-based activity or experience, which encourages students to develop skills and concepts. The teacher's role is one of facilitator or consultant. In addition, students are encouraged to work in a cooperative learning environment without direct instruction from the teacher. This phase is also unique because the students are given a "hands-on" experience before any formal explanation of terms, definitions, or concepts are discussed or explained by the teacher.</p> <p>They identify and develop concepts, processes, and skills. During this phase, students actively explore their environment or manipulate materials.</p>
Explain	<p>This phase of the 5 E's helps students explain the concepts they have been exploring.</p> <p>A "minds-on" phase follows the exploration phase, and this is more teacher-directed and guided by the students' prior experience during the exploration phase. The explanation phase enables students to describe their understanding and pose questions about the concepts they have been exploring. They have opportunities to verbalize their conceptual understanding or to demonstrate new skills or behaviors. It is likely that new questions will be generated. The explanation phase is an essential, minds-on part of the 5E lesson. Before the teacher attempts to provide an explanation, the students must first have the opportunity to express their own explanations and ideas. Thus, the initial part of the explanation phase is a time for the teacher to serve as a facilitator and ask the students to describe and discuss their exploration learning experiences.</p> <p>After the students have had the opportunity to share their own explanations, the teacher introduces scientific and technical information in a direct manner. This phase includes clarification of student misconceptions that may have emerged during the engagement or exploration phases. Formal definitions, notes, and labels are provided. This phase provides opportunities for teachers to introduce formal terms, definitions, and explanations for concepts, processes, skills, or behaviors. The teacher may also decide to integrate video, computer software programs, or other visual aides to help with student understanding. The students should then be able to clearly explain the important concepts to the teacher and to their peers.</p>
Elaborate	<p>The activities in this phase of the learning cycle should encourage students to apply their new understanding of concepts, while reinforcing new skills.</p> <p>This phase of the 5 E's extends students' conceptual understanding and allows them to practice skills and behaviors. Students are encouraged to check for understanding with their peers, or to design new experiments or models based on the new skills or concepts they have acquired.</p> <p>Through new experiences, the learners develop deeper and broader understanding of major concepts, obtain more information about areas of interest, and refine their skills.</p> <p>Students may conduct additional investigations, develop products, share information and ideas, or apply their knowledge and skills to other disciplines. This is a great opportunity to integrate science with other content areas. Elaboration activities may also integrate technology.</p>
Evaluate	<p>This phase of the 5 E's encourages learners to assess their understanding and abilities and lets teachers evaluate students' understanding of key concepts and skill development.</p> <p>Assessment in an inquiry-based setting is very different to that in traditional science lessons. Both formal and informal assessment approaches are appropriate and should be included. For instance, the use of non-traditional forms of assessment, such as portfolios, performance-based assessment, concept maps, physical models, or journal logs may serve as significant evidence of student learning. During an inquiry-based lesson, assessment should be viewed as an ongoing process, with teachers making observations of their students as they apply new concepts and skills and looking for evidence that the students have changed or modified their thinking. Students may also have the opportunity to conduct self-assessment or</p>

	peer-assessment. However, the evaluation may also include a summative experience such as a quiz, exam, or writing assignment.
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Table 42. 5E Instructional Learning Cycle

Targets All the actors involved in the Circular Economy concept and in the minimum, Public Authorities, Citizen, Industry and Scholars.

Although the 5E Model has just been explained in serial order, it is often necessary to reverse back into the cycle before again going forward. For instance, numerous explore/explain rotations may need to occur before the students are ready to transition to the elaboration phase. The teacher may move back and forth several times within the Es or may include an additional engagement prior to starting an elaboration phase. The cycle is very flexible and dynamic. It may take many days to complete the lesson or unit. It is not necessary to complete one learning cycle each day that science is taught. The model is designed to facilitate conceptual change and contribute to more consistent and coherent science instruction (Bybee, 1997)³³.

The 5E instructional planning model has been integrated, as a core instructional design strategy, in many science classrooms with the following major goals:

- provide effective and sustained professional development in science content, pedagogy, and assessment for elementary teachers,
- implement quality inquiry-based science curriculum and instruction,
- coordinate curriculum, classroom practice, and student assessment with the district-adopted science courses of study and statewide curriculum models and assessments, and
- enhance the science content knowledge of elementary teachers in life, physical, and earth/space science.

The 5E planning guide enables teachers to personalize lessons according to student needs. Educators often teach chapters or units from the order that is presented in the book. However, various and flexible teaching enables children with attention problems to stay focused. The 5E Model is a tool for teachers to engage the students with topics they may not have much interest in or prior knowledge about.

In order for students to learn and gain an understanding of science concepts, they must be actively engaged in their own learning. They must be led by their teacher to discover things. Teachers must guide their students in directions that will help them observe/discover to correct

³³ Bybee, R. (1997). *Achieving scientific literacy: From purposes to practices*. Portsmouth, NH: Heinemann Publications.

their own misconceptions. It is this inquiry learning that leads to true learning. A 5E plan helps set-up lessons in a manner that supports this type of teaching.

The 5E methodology has been adapted in a simplified way based on Virtualware previous experiences to better fit to schools' data capture needs in following steps:

- **Information:** It is a phase where user need to have previous knowledges and information as basic theory. So, in this phase, user learn this information.
- **Exploration:** In this phase user researches about:
 - Problem or situation described
 - Hypothesis
- **Creation:** It will be a creation to show how to solve the problem situation.

Figure 9. Method implemented

In parallel and transversally it will be defined:

- 360 evaluations
- Auto-evaluation
- Group Evaluation
- Teacher evaluation
-

Moreover, all the areas identified as priorities will be part of the 6 Digital Project because of students can work these items always.

ANNEX II - QUESTIONNAIRE

URBAN SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT

Data Capture form for waste4think Project. Data to be collected are:

- Contact details of the educational centre for effective communication.
- Contact details of the educational centre that allows to know the state of the art and the possibilities and interest of adopting new measures, resources or dynamics to improve its current situation.
- To make it possible to know the reality of urban solid waste management in educational centres.
- Regarding how this theme is integrated into the educational centre ecosystem: Unique actions, integration in the curriculum, innovative projects, systematic actions, with respect to reduction, reuse and recycling of urban waste.

The data will be used for designing educational projects (educational units, educational digital objects and mobile app) within the Waste4things project.

Informed Consent Clause.

Thank you for Reading this information

We would like you to participate in a survey about waste management habits within the Waste4Think project by filling this questionnaire. It is voluntary, but your answers will be of great value for the development of the educational materials that will be generated within the project.

We only need the e-mail of a contact person to have a partner along the project. We do not need any further information; The questionnaire can be completed in an anonymous way. Although we will not be processing any identifying information, stored data will be treated in a way that ensures confidentiality.

The survey will be saved to know the evolution of the habits about waste management in educational centres along project life-time (4 years). The questionnaires will be stored in a Virtualware server in Basauri.

Personal data (such as e-mail of the responsible) will only be accessible for the research team.

The research results are part of a survey with the aim of improving waste management at council level, reducing waste generation and promoting good habits for separating, preventing and reusing waste. If you have any questions, you can contact Leire Armentia (larmenia@virtualwaregroup.com)

Do you agree in taking part in this survey? YES, NO, OTHER

I do confirm that I have read the consent clause and I accept the terms of use of data collected in the survey YES, NO

GENERAL CENTRE DATA

EDUCATIONAL CENTRE NAME

LEVELS OF EDUCATION

- Primary education
- Secondary education (1st grade, 2st grade, 3st grade)
- Tertiary education
- Vocational education and training
- Other

<http://www.ekep.gr/english/education/diagramma.asp>

Indicate the number of students by educational level

Choose which of the following facilities are available in your school and generate this type of waste:

- Kitchen
- Catering
- Student Kitchen
- School Dining room
- GYM
- Laboratory
- Art class
- OTHER

What educational methodology have you implemented?

- Learning by projects
- Scientific methodology
- MasterClasses
- Other:

Personal data protection Policy

If you are interested in participating actively in a team to improve waste management in your municipality, by the actions developed from your school, you can give us your email, telephone number and date / time to contact.

Under Law 15/1999 on Protection of Personal Data (LOPD) and Law 34/2002 on Services of the information and Electronic Commerce Virtualware 2007 S.A. (Hereinafter the Owner) located in the Poligono Artunduaga -C / Usausuaga, 7, 48970, Basauri, Bizkaia, informs you that the personal data you provide to us by any means, including electronic mail, or Data forms, will be stored in a file for automated processing or automated, in order to proceed with your requests and provide the information about Waste4Think Project. You can exercise your rights of access, rectification, cancellation and opposition by writing to the above address or via email larmenia@virtualwaregroup.com.

Personal data of responsible in WASTE4THINK Project

(Include name, e-mail, telephone and time to contact). With this data I accept the above Data Use Policy

TECHNOLOGY

Tell us which technological resources, web applications and apps use regularly in your School

At the technological and infrastructure level select the answers that fit the reality of the school

- We use PCs
- We use Android TABLETS
- We use IPADS
- WIFI with weak signal
- WIFI without network problems
- Mobile Devices are allowed in class for students
- Students have access to market for downloading APPs in Tablets
- Teachers are responsible for downloading apps in market
- We don't download apps, We only work with digital educational units available on website.
- We are interested in robotics and we teach it in school
- We are interested in robotics but we don't teach it in class
- We are interested in programming and we teach it in class
- We are interested in programming but we don't teach it in class
- We have laboratory

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D4.3

- We have laboratory with access for students.
- We have to allow the acces to specific webpages in order not to access to inadequate content.
- Other:

Which software, digital applications and standards do you use or know for teaching in class?

- Goggle drive
- Microsoft
- Linux
- Open source APPS
- iOS
- Voki
- Prezi
- GoogleMaps
- Scratch
- Flickr
- Creativecommons
- Augmented Reality
- Interative Gynkhanas
- Casual Games
- Gamificación Gamification
- Other:

WASTE MANAMENT IN THE EDUCATIONAL CENTRE

Reality and concerns regarding waste management

Do you know what is the solid waste management more similar to urban?

YES/NO/OTHER

Do you manage solid waste similar to urban in the School?

YES/NO/SOMETIMES/OTHER

Who are the responsible to move away waste in the school?

- Nursery school teacher – Kindegarden
- Students / Teachers
- Primary Education Students
- Primary Education Teachers
- Secondary Education Students

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D4.3

- Secondary Education Teachers
- Tertiary Education Students
- Tertiary Education Teachers
- Vocational education and training students
- Vocational education and training teachers
- Cleaning Staff
- Kitchen Staff
- Management staff
- Other:

At the level of waste separation Which resources do you have?

- Containers out of educational centre for choosing waste
- Bins in classroom for waste selection
- Bins in dining room for waste selection.
- Bins in Laboratory for waste selection.
- Compost Bin
- Agreements for reusing of waste
- green purchasing
- Local trade/
- Bulk purchase
- Other:

Which of these topics would you like to work in educational centre?

Select your preference from 0 (nothing) to 5 (all)

- Know correct classification guidelines.
- Know the amount of waste that we generate
- Automate classification and proper waste management
- Automate data collection (amount of waste generated, amount of waste managed ...)
- Learn how to manage waste through gaming.
- How do you affect the correct / incorrect management affects in our neighborhood, town, planet. Impact of individual actions over environment.
- We need to know, regarding to other schools, towns, countries how strong we are in waste management

Use ICT to better manage

- Waste and art.
- Waste and audiovisual communication

Deliverable
D4.3

- Work autonomy and empowerment of people.
- Waste, programming and robotics.
- Waste, the current public regulations and the possibility of modifying it to allow more efficient and sustainable management systems.

Do you save waste generation data?

- Yes, we do it in a systematic way.
- Yes, we do it but not in a systematic way
- No, we don't

Which kind of waste is generated in your educational centre?

- Papel PAPER
- Plastic
- Gardening waste
- Package
- swaddling clothes
- Food
- paperboard
- Sanitary waste (compresses ...)
- Other:

Which type of data do you save? Since when? How Often? which format do you save? Who is in charge of saving these data? For what purpose?

Your answer

Do you have school garden?

- Yes, It is running
- Yes, we have, but we don't use it
- NO

If you don't use school garden, please tell the reason and if you are interesting on re-using it again.

Your answer

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D4.3

Do you have compost bin?

- YES
- No

Which data from compost bin do you save?

- Temperature
- Humidity
- Amount of compost generated
- Other:

Do you save any other data regarding to sustainable consumption? which data? How do you get them up?

Your answer

Are there any specific actions regarding to waste management separation in classroom? Activities in and out of classroom, projects, which level of acceptance do they have?

STAFF

We want to know who can help in order to project runs

which educational level do you think the project can work better for? (For sensitivity, time, provision of teachers ...).

- Nursery School
- Primary education
- Secondary Education
- Tertiary education

<http://www.ekep.gr/english/education/diagramma.asp>

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D4.3

Are you interested in students and teachers participating in a survey to collect data for designing games for mobile devices?

- Yes, we are interested but only with students' participation.
- Yes, we are interested but only with teachers' participation.
- Both of them

ANNEX III - EXTRA REFERENCES FOR DIGITAL PROJECT 2

SAN FRANCISCO 0 WASTE

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Cg3OA1s8-SI>

Compost waste resources

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nYDQcBQUdpw>

0 waste town

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eym10GGidQU>

Resource

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Kr_DGf77OhM

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=p5QBKUU_47E

https://www.youtube.com/watch?time_continue=47&v=RstFV_n6wRg

Circular Economy

https://www.youtube.com/watch?time_continue=47&v=RstFV_n6wRg

- Hierarchy concept of priority, prevention and reusability (Used by one person to another), preparation for reusing what has already being thrown in the collection service (it is already waste, it is in the collection service, I do not want it, the collection service prepares it - cleaning, checking, repairing and finally, will be reused as a product), recycled ... Use it as a tip to analyze the photo.

- <http://www.return-to-value.com/es/de-residuo-recurso>

Basuria

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=M3z-YPsumOw>

Deliverable
D4.3

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ANNEX IV - DIGITAL PROJECT 2 - TEMPLATES

Footprint identification template

MAMMALS IDENTIFICATION FORM ACCORDING TO THEIR FOOTPRINT

<https://www.uv.es/zoobot/huellas/fichas.html>

shutterstock

IMAGE ID: 552731050
www.shutterstock.com

Research template

INVESTIGATION WASTEY RESEARCH		
NAME OF THE RESEARCH TEAM		
NAME FOR PERSONS INVOLVED AND ASSOCIATED TASKS	NAME	TASK
WORK HYPOTHESIS		
SELECTED HYPOTHESIS		
METHODOLOGY (MÁX 5 LINES)		

<p>RESULTS.</p> <p>(Including results of the obtained data and images of the working process followed).</p>	
<p>CONCLUSIONS (Indicating if the selected hypothesis has been validated and write down other conclusions)</p>	

Research rules

RESEARCH RULES	
1	Between day 1 and 5, only a visual analysis of the bins can be carried out Which kind of waste is inside each of them? Is there any kind of waste that should not be there? Is there any food?
2	Between day 1 and 5, bin can only be touched to weigh it
3	The content of the bin can only be touch if it is out of it.
4	Waste must be collected from the floor and placed in the corresponding bins.
5	There is only one chance to capture the guilty. It's the sixth day of research
6	Everyday 1 person from each team will go to the data collection.
7	1 person will place the scale, another one will collect waste and classify it with the help of the rest of the people. The others will collect data.

EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS Check that you have the following materials available

- **DATA CAPTURE WASTEY.** To record the everyday data of each day of the research.
- **WASTEY RESEARCH MAP.** To identify where the bins are, give them a number and show where the animal has appeared and where you think it will appear again.
- **WASTEY RESEARCH TEMPLATE.** To collect general data of the research process.

PAPER BIN TYPE AND WHERE TO THROW EACH WASTE TYPE (According to the collection procedure of each municipality).

In each classroom you can find the following bins

Paper bin. Clean paper used on both sides

Plastic bin. I.e. Plastic containers, albal and juice bricks.

Food Waste bin. uncooked food remainings, plants or other gardening pruning (apples, banana skin ...)

Bin for other type of waste. Everything that can not be included in the rest of the bins.

Battery collection. Worn batteries that are not rechargeable.

Data capture template

WASTEY – RESEARCH TEMPLATE															
RESEARCH GENERAL DATA															
NAME OF THE RESEARCH TEAM															
TEAM MEMBERS															
HYPOTHESIS TO BE VALIDATED															
BINS (ADD AS MANY AS NEEDED)	BIN 1 (INDICATE THE TYPE OF WASTE. PAPER, PLASTIC, ORGANIC, THE REST)			BIN 2 (INDICATE THE TYPE OF WASTE. PAPER, PLASTIC, ORGANIC, THE REST)			BIN 3 (INDICATE THE TYPE OF WASTE. PAPER, PLASTIC, ORGANIC, THE REST)			BIN 3 (INDICATE THE TYPE OF WASTE. PAPER, PLASTIC, ORGANIC, THE REST)			BIN 3 (INDICATE THE TYPE OF WASTE. PAPER, PLASTIC, ORGANIC, THE REST)		
WASTEY DATA COLLECTION	BIN WEIGHT (gr)	TYPE OF RESOURCE	MOUSE TRACE. YES/NO	BIN WEIGHT (gr)	TYPE OF RESOURCE	MOUSE TRACE. YES/NO	BIN WEIGHT (gr)	TYPE OF RESOURCE	MOUSE TRACE. YES/NO	BIN WEIGHT (gr)	TYPE OF RESOURCE	MOUSE TRACE. YES/NO	BIN WEIGHT (gr)	TYPE OF RESOURCE	MOUSE TRACE. YES/NO
DAY1. (Person in charge of data collection)															

VALIDATED HIPOTHESYS	
EXPLAIN YOUR REASONS TO ACCEPT OR REJECT THE HYPOTHESIS	
NOTES	

Research Map

Adjust this design to your school center (you can make your own sketch by hand). Please, indicate on the map where the classrooms you are investigating are located. Then write down **where the mouse has appeared** everyday day and **try to foresee where the next day it will appear**. Suggestion: Use different colors to better keep tracking.

